

TERRA VISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

D7.2

Framework of processing Analysis Ready Data

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOI	Area Of Interest
API	Application Programming Interface
ARD	Analysis Ready Data
AOI	Area of Interest
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architecture
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
GCP	Ground Control Point
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LIDAR	Laser imaging, detection, and ranging
LULC	Land Use Land Cover
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
NBR	Normalized Burn Ratio
ROI	Region Of Interest
RPC	Rational Polynomial Coefficients
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SoTA	State of The Art
TOI	Time of interest
VLM	Vision Language Model

H1 – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document defines the TERRAVISION Analysis Ready Data (ARD) FRAMEWORK. The aim of this framework is to support and enhance the development and provision of novel services. A central element of this work is a four-layer architecture, designated TERRAVISION LAYER (TL) TL1 through TL4. Through this layered system, diverse raw Earth Observation inputs, which include satellite imagery (such as Sentinel-2 and PRISMA), airborne observational data, and information from in-situ Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, are systematically ingested, processed, and transformed into valuable, actionable information.

The document's structure is designed to guide progressively through the framework's conception, implementation, and operational context. It commences with an Introduction (Section 1), wherein the specific scope of this deliverable, its intended purpose within the project's lifecycle, the target readership, and its interconnectedness with other work packages and deliverables are clearly articulated, setting the context for the subsequent technical expositions. The Requirements (Section 2) are then defined. This section details the diverse demands imposed upon the Analysis Ready Data framework by the various Earth Observation services under development in related work packages (specifically WP9-10), spanning applications from raw material exploration to dynamic hazard prediction, thereby establishing the performance and functionality benchmarks for the ARD system.

Subsequently, the Framework High-Level Design (Section 3) is presented. This part introduces the overarching conceptual architecture, emphasizing the modular, scalable, and interoperable four-layer structure (TL1 through TL4) designed to process heterogeneous data sources systematically, from raw ingestion to semantic interpretation, forming the backbone of the TERRAVISION data processing pipeline. A comprehensive and granular explanation of the Framework Implementation (Section 4) follows. This substantial section details the system architecture, covering key design principles such as modularity, configurability via a human-readable JSON schema, extensibility through a robust class registry and plugin architecture, reproducibility ensured by managed dependencies (requirements.txt) and environment configurations (.env files), and a strong focus on performance, often leveraging GPU acceleration for computationally intensive tasks.

Within Section 4, a deep dive into each of the four TERRAVISION Layers is provided:

- **TL1 (Ingestion Layer):** Its responsibilities for the robust ingestion, thorough validation (e.g., file integrity, format consistency), and systematic normalization of varied raw data streams, including complex satellite datacubes (e.g., Sentinel-2), high-resolution airborne imagery, and ancillary Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), are detailed. The objective is to transform these inputs into a consistent, well-defined in-memory format, often utilizing libraries like xarray for efficient multi-dimensional data manipulation.
- **TL2 (Pre-processing Layer):** This layer's pivotal role in elevating the normalized outputs of TL1 to genuine Analysis Ready Data is explained. It orchestrates a sequence of critical radiometric and geometric corrections. Alpha-versions of sophisticated algorithms, including cloud and shadow masking (employing techniques informed by

SCR-DIP and utilizing Scene Classification Layers (SCL) for Sentinel-2 data) and orthorectification (drawing from Orbview principles and reliant on Rational Polynomial Coefficients (RPCs) and DEMs), are described. The layer is also designed to accommodate other essential corrections.

- **TL3 (Feature Analysis & Inference Layer):** The function of this layer in harnessing the ARD generated by TL2 to execute a suite of advanced AI-driven analytical models is outlined. The document details the alpha-versions of powerful algorithms for tasks such as object detection (utilizing models like Detrex and GroundedSAM2 for identifying specific features of interest within mining sites) and change detection (leveraging specialized architectures like MineNetCD).
- **TL4 (Fusion Layer):** As the final stage, TL4's responsibility for the intelligent collation, fusion, and sophisticated post-processing of the rich outputs generated by the preceding layers is covered. It is designed to produce not only fused data products but also to generate semantically rich narratives and facilitate Visual Question Answering (VQA) systems, exemplified by the fine-tuned LLaVA Custom model.

Section 4 also covers core software abstractions and interfaces, the mechanics of the JSON-driven configuration, the class registry that enables the plugin architecture, environment and dependency management practices, testing and validation strategies, guidance on extending the codebase, an illustrative case study of an example pipeline run using a Streamlit interface, and details on utility scripts for data acquisition. These utilities include methods for downloading Sentinel-2 data via OpenEO from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem, handling EnMAP and PRISMA hyperspectral data (noting PRISMA's geolocation challenges), and processing various types of airborne data supplied by DIMAP (LiDAR, RGB, Thermal, Hyperspectral).

A Theoretical Description of Alpha-version Algorithms (Section 5) is provided. This segment delves into the methodologies and operational principles underpinning key algorithms that have been implemented in their initial versions. Specific attention is given to the Cloud Masking approach, which draws from the SCR-DIP model, detailing its per-image optimization without extensive prior training, and the Orthorectification process, informed by Orbview concepts, which utilizes RPCs and DEMs primarily for PRISMA data. The section on Pilots testing (Section 6) is structured to summarize tests conducted using the framework with data from each pilot site (Canteras, Tharsis, Terna Mag) across various image sources, although the current deliverable notes this as an area for more extensive future reporting as algorithm maturity increases. A Comparison of TERRAVISION's ARD Framework with other approaches (Section 7) is then undertaken. This comparative analysis positions the TERRAVISION system relative to current state-of-the-art ARD generation initiatives, underscoring the novel integration of semantic techniques and Artificial Intelligence directly within the data processing lifecycle, particularly in TL3 and TL4, thereby aiming for ARD that is not just 'AI-ready' but inherently 'AI-derived and semantically-rich'. Guidance on the progression Towards the final version (Section 8) is detailed. This section discusses the current advanced alpha developmental status of the framework and outlines the planned subsequent steps. These include iterative refinement and comprehensive validation of all algorithms, integration of remaining functionalities like full in-situ sensor data pipelines, performance enhancements,

and strategies for full-scale pilot testing and feedback incorporation. The Conclusion (Section 9) then recapitulates the major achievements, the current standing of the framework, and the forward path towards its final operational deployment. Standard supporting sections such as Bibliography and Annexes are also included to provide references and supplementary information.

The system's design has resulted in an advanced alpha stage where core architectural components and pivotal alpha-version algorithms across all layers have been implemented and subjected to initial validation. The codebase supporting this endeavor has been made available on GitHub. A key innovation presented is the intrinsic integration of artificial intelligence and semantic techniques throughout the data lifecycle. Future progression will be characterized by iterative algorithm refinement, comprehensive validation, the seamless integration of remaining functionalities, and robust performance optimization, ensuring the delivery of a practical and impactful tool for the mining industry.

H2 – GOAL/OBJECTIVES

The primary goal of this deliverable, is to establish and implement an innovative, integrated high-quality Analysis Ready Data (ARD) FRAMEWORK and derive actionable, insightful information from a diverse array of sources, including satellite imagery, airborne data, and in-situ sensors. This is specifically aimed at developing and providing novel services designed to fundamentally enhance and support every phase of the mining life cycle for critical raw materials. The framework aims to streamline and standardize the entire data preprocessing pipeline, transforming raw observations into harmonized, reliable, and semantically enriched datasets that can be efficiently exploited to foster sustainable management practices and improve decision-making within the complex domain of mining.

H3 – METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in the development and implementation of the TERRAVISION Analysis Ready Data (ARD) framework is multifaceted, centered on a systematic, layered architectural design and iterative development practices. This approach ensures a robust, flexible, and extensible system capable of processing diverse Earth Observation data for the mining lifecycle.

- **Layered Architectural Design:** The core of the methodology was the adoption of a four-layer architecture (TL1-TL4). This design choice systematically segregates functionalities:
 - TL1 (Ingestion Layer): Methodologically focused on creating robust ingestion pipelines for various raw data formats (e.g., Sentinel-2 NetCDF, airborne BSQ/HDR, DEMs). This involved implementing procedures for data validation, metadata extraction, and normalization into a consistent in-memory representation (e.g., xarray Datasets) to serve as a unified foundation for subsequent processing.

- TL2 (Pre-processing Layer): The methodology here involved identifying essential radiometric and geometric corrections and implementing them as modular algorithms. This included the adaptation and initial implementation of established techniques like cloud masking (informed by SCR-DIP, utilizing SCL bands for Sentinel-2) and orthorectification (drawing from Orbview principles, using RPCs and DEMs, particularly for PRISMA data). The approach allowed for selective application of these corrections based on data source and user needs.
- TL3 (Feature Analysis & Inference Layer): This layer's methodology centered on integrating advanced AI-driven analytical models. It involved selecting and implementing alpha-versions of algorithms for object detection (e.g., Detrex, GroundedSAM2) and change detection (e.g., MineNetCD), and defining interfaces to allow these models to consume ARD from TL2 and produce semantic outputs.
- TL4 (Fusion Layer): The methodology for this final layer focused on the intelligent collation, fusion of multi-source information, and sophisticated post-processing. This included developing capabilities for generating semantically rich narratives and enabling Visual Question Answering (VQA) systems (e.g., through a fine-tuned LLaVA custom model) to translate complex data into human-understandable insights.
- **Modular and Extensible Software Development.** A key methodological principle was the development of a modular and extensible system. This was achieved through:
 - JSON-Driven Configuration: Implementing a system where pipeline behaviour (inputs, algorithm selection, hyperparameters, outputs) is defined in human-readable JSON files. This decouples pipeline definition from code, enhancing reproducibility and adaptability.
 - Class Registry and Plugin Architecture: A central CLASS_REGISTRY was established, allowing algorithms to be registered and dynamically loaded based on the JSON configuration. This methodology facilitates the easy addition or modification of processing modules without altering core framework code.
 - Standardized Interfaces: Defining abstract base classes and consistent interfaces for each layer (e.g., TL1_Input, TL2_Algorithm) ensured that components could be developed and tested independently and integrated seamlessly.
- **Iterative Development and Validation:** The framework was developed using an iterative methodology.
 - Alpha-Version Implementation: Initial versions of key algorithms were developed and integrated to establish baseline functionality and validate architectural choices.
 - Pilot Testing: Data from the designated pilot sites (Canteras, Tharsis, Terna Mag) were used for initial testing and validation of the framework and its algorithms. This provided early feedback for refinement.
 - Progressive Enhancement: The "Towards the final version" section outlines a methodological plan for continued refinement, comprehensive validation

against KPIs, integration of remaining algorithms, expansion of training datasets for AI models, and full operationalization of all data pipelines (including in-situ sensors).

- **Data Acquisition and Management.** The methodology for data acquisition involved:
 - Utilizing OpenEO for standardized access to Copernicus Sentinel-2 L2A data, including on-the-fly cloud masking.
 - Establishing procedures for handling diverse airborne data formats from DIMAP.
 - Planning for the integration of PRISMA and EnMAP hyperspectral data, and future in-situ sensor data.
 - Outputting processed data in standard formats like NetCDF for interoperability.
- **Software Engineering Best Practices.** The development methodology adhered to standard software engineering practices, including:
 - Version Control: Utilizing GitHub for collaborative development and codebase management.
 - Dependency Management: Employing requirements.txt for consistent and reproducible environments.
 - Environment Configuration: Using .env files for managing machine-specific and sensitive configurations.
 - Testing: Implementing initial unit testing procedures to ensure component reliability.
- **Focus on Semantic Integration and AI:** A distinct methodological aspect was the deep and early integration of AI and semantic understanding capabilities directly within the ARD processing chain (TL3 and TL4), rather than treating these as subsequent, separate analytical steps. This aims to produce ARD that is "AI-derived and semantically-rich," moving beyond traditional "AI-ready" data.

This comprehensive methodology ensures the development of a robust, adaptable, and powerful framework tailored to the specific needs of enhancing the mining life cycle through advanced Earth Observation data processing.

H4 – OUTCOMES/CONCLUSIONS

The TERRAVISION ARD framework development has successfully resulted in an advanced v1 platform, demonstrating a robust four-layer architecture capable of ingesting, pre-processing, analyzing, and semantically interpreting diverse Earth Observation data, this deliverable is focus in L2 and in the global architecture. Key outcomes include the operationalization of this modular system, managed by a flexible JSON-driven configuration, and the initial implementation and validation of critical algorithms for cloud masking, orthorectification, object detection, change detection, and semantic narrative generation using data from the pilot mining sites. The framework's design, emphasizing extensibility and AI integration, distinctly positions it to produce "AI-derived and semantically-rich" ARD, moving beyond traditional data readiness. However, it is concluded that substantial work remains to achieve

the final, fully operational platform. This includes the iterative refinement and comprehensive validation of all algorithms, the seamless integration of remaining functionalities such as full in-situ sensor data pipelines, rigorous performance optimization, and extensive pilot testing. While the current outcomes affirm the framework's significant potential to deliver enhanced, actionable insights for the mining life cycle, dedicated effort is required to transition from this promising version 1 to version 2 final tool.

Key outcomes/conclusions in bullet points

1. **functional Alpha Framework:** A four-layer ARD processing framework is operational at an advanced alpha stage.
2. **Modular & Configurable:** The system is modular and managed by a flexible JSON configuration.
3. **Initial Algorithms Implemented:** Key algorithms for pre-processing (cloud masking, orthorectification) and AI-driven analysis (object detection, semantic narration) are implemented in alpha versions.

1. Introduction

1.1 Deliverable Description

This deliverable provides a comprehensive exposition of the TERRAVISION project's framework implemented for the generation of Analysis Ready Data (ARD). Sourced from a diverse array of Earth Observation (EO) inputs, encompassing raw satellite imagery (such as Sentinel-2, PRISMA, and others...), specialized airborne observational data and IoT information, this framework is engineered to fundamentally streamline and standardize the entire data preprocessing pipeline. Its specific application focus is on delivering novel services that enhance the entire mining life cycle of critical raw materials, a domain demanding robust, reliable, and actionable geospatial information.

The core of this framework is architected around four distinct and sequentially-executed TERRAVISION Layers, hereafter denominated TL1, TL2, TL3, and TL4. Each layer represents a progressive stage of data transformation and analytical enrichment, orchestrated through, human-readable, JSON-driven configuration system. This document meticulously details the specific implementation choices, methodologies, and algorithmic components realized within each of these layers. The complete codebase underpinning this framework, demonstrating its practical realization, is actively managed and accessible via a dedicated GitHub repository (the specifics of which, including access and structure, are further elaborated in sections like 3.1.10, "Case study: example pipeline run" which often includes execution commands, and implicitly through discussions on environment and dependency management in 3.1.7).

The progression through the TERRAVISION Layers is as follows:

- **TERRAVISION Layer 1 (TL1) (Ingestion Layer):** This foundational layer is responsible for the critical first steps of data handling. It focuses on the robust ingestion.
- **TERRAVISION Layer 2 (TL2) (Pre-processing Layer):** Building upon the normalized outputs of TL1, this layer is pivotal in elevating these raw inputs to genuine Analysis Ready Data. It orchestrates a sequence of critical radiometric and geometric corrections.
- **TERRAVISION Layer 3 (TL3) (Feature Analysis & Inference Layer):** This layer harnesses the ARD generated by TL2 to execute a suite of advanced AI-driven analytical models, moving from data preparation to information extraction.
- **TERRAVISION Layer 4 (TL4) (Fusion Layer):** As the final stage, TL4 is responsible for the intelligent collation, fusion, and sophisticated post-processing of the rich outputs generated by the preceding layers.

Beyond the layer-specific implementations, this document provides an outline of the overarching system architecture, detailing its core design principles: modularity for ease of development and maintenance, configurability for adaptability to diverse use-cases, extensibility via a class registry and plugin architecture for future enhancements, reproducibility to ensure scientific validity, and performance optimization for operational viability. Furthermore, it presents the current status of the alpha-versions of key algorithms that have been developed, integrated, and tested within these TERRAVISION Layers.

The overarching ambition of this framework is to significantly reduce the preprocessing traditionally faced by TERRAVISION Service providers, particularly within the complex domain of the project.

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

This document provides the specification for the Analysis Ready Data (ARD) processing chain that underpins every TERRAVISION demonstrator. It converts the broad objectives of Work Packages 7 and 8, namely satellite pre-processing, multi-sensor fusion, and AI-ready outputs, into a single, end-to-end architecture. By describing each step in the four-level workflow, it ensures that raw observations are systematically transformed into harmonised, high-quality datasets that any partner or external user can exploit without duplicating effort.

Beyond defining the technical sequence, the deliverable serves as a shared reference that aligns the work of ITA, ICCS, SINTEF, AUTH, TERRADUE, AURORA, GEOS and DIMAP. Every algorithm, interface and quality checkpoint are laid out in enough detail for teams to develop modules independently while guaranteeing seamless interoperability once those modules are integrated.

The text also marks the transition from the initial prototype (Part A) to the final operational chain (Part B). Lessons learned during early test deployments have been incorporated, locking down performance targets, data formats and key performance indicators so that subsequent tasks can proceed on a stable foundation.

Full, transparent documentation of algorithms, parameter choices, metadata schemas and the semantic layer gives the framework auditability and reproducibility. Researchers, industry stakeholders and policymakers will be able to trace any process pipeline back to its origin, rerun the processing if necessary, and have confidence that results comply with emerging ARD standards.

Finally, the deliverable links the ARD pipeline to the project's broader goals by specifying how calibrated spectral signatures are stored in the Raw-Material Spectral Knowledge Database. This guarantees that downstream models, such as super-resolution, hazard mapping and CoreSmart metal-grade estimation, can draw on a reliable, standardised repository, anchoring all later technical developments, demonstrations and exploitation activities.

1.3 Intended Audience

This deliverable is primarily aimed at service providers, those for whom value-added TERRAVISION applications are being developed. Examples might include environmental monitoring dashboards, decision-support tools for exploration, or automated reporting pipelines. It should be noted that a precise and stable description of the Analysis Ready Data is provided, allowing these providers to fully understand what will be ingested into their systems.

Full visibility is ensured regarding the processing levels, the metadata schema, semantic annotations, and all relevant quality checkpoints. As a result, algorithms, APIs, and user

interfaces can be designed with the confidence that input imagery will be delivered in a harmonised and thoroughly documented format across every TERRAVISION demonstrator.

1.4 Deliverable structure and relation with other work packages/deliverables

This document, D7.2 "Framework of processing Analysis Ready Data," details the TERRAVISION ARD processing framework, building upon the state-of-the-art review presented in D7.1 "State of the Art in ARD." For detailed explanations of the semantic layers (TL3 and TL4), are described in D7.5 "Pixel and Feature level models (Alpha version)."

The document is structured as follows:

- **Introduction:** Outlines the deliverable's scope, purpose, audience, and relation to other project components.
- **Requirements:** Specifies the demands placed on the ARD framework by TERRAVISION services.
- **Framework High-level Design:** Presents the conceptual four-layer architecture (TL1-TL4).
- **Framework Implementation:** System architecture (design principles, data flow).
- **Alpha-version Algorithms Theoretical Description:** Explains principles behind key implemented pre-processing algorithms for TL2 (e.g., Cloud Masking, Orthorectification).
- **Pilots testing:** Briefly outlines tests conducted with data from pilot sites.
- **TERRAVISION's ARD Framework vs other approaches:** Compares the framework to existing ARD solutions, highlighting its integrated AI/semantic approach.
- **Towards the final version:** Discusses the current status and roadmap for future development.
- **Conclusion:** Summarizes the main achievements and outlook.
- **Bibliography & Annexes:** Supporting references and additional information.

2. Requirements

The various EO services being developed in WP9-10 of the TERRAVISION project place a set of various demands on the ARD framework. These services span raw material exploration (T9.1), surface deformation monitoring (T9.2), extraction rate estimation (T9.3), primary and secondary material mapping (T9.4), and dynamic hazard prediction (T9.5). Each of these services introduces a distinct interaction with remote sensing data, and their specific requirements on the ARD framework being not only present, but sufficiently tailored in accuracy, temporal consistency, sensor harmonization, and accessibility. The role of the ARD framework is therefore not one of passive data delivery but one of active, context-aware preprocessing that transforms raw multisensory data into semantically and geometrically coherent outputs.

In raw material exploration under T9.1, high-resolution optical data from Sentinel-2 and hyperspectral sources must first be normalized for clouds, shadow, and view angle disparities before any meaningful spectral analysis can be performed. The spectral integrity of the data is essential for target definition and lithological classification, as mineral types can only be distinguished through narrow reflectance differences. Without a consistent and artifact-free ARD input spectral diagnostics may become unreliable, especially when conducting regional explorations that aggregate data over time and across sensors. Orthorectification of the source imagery using DEMs and geometric models is also essential. In rugged terrain or in open-pit mines with large elevation gradients, geometric distortion can significantly impair spatial alignment between satellite data and ground-truth observations or in-situ spectral collections. Spatial misalignment would disrupt the fusion of airborne hyperspectral scans and field-collected spectral samples. The same goes for co-registration of temporal stacks that enables trend detection and consistency in time-series used by raw material exploration.

The task T9.3 regarding extraction rate estimation also integrates services that operate directly on outputs processed with TL2. The very first requirement here is the generation of high-fidelity 3D models through photogrammetric reconstruction, for which cloud-free, geometrically stable imagery is essential. Stereo pair processing to derive elevation models is particularly sensitive to noise in image borders, artifacts caused by atmospheric scattering, and inconsistent acquisition parameters. The cloud masking and orthorectification performed in TL2 help with the successful reconstruction of mine topography, and thus the estimation of extracted volumes. These models also need to be anchored against in-situ reference data such as LiDAR, meaning the image-to-ground registration must be reliable across multiple scales.

The task T9.4 about primary and secondary material mapping also needs TL2 processed outputs because of the necessity to align datasets over large spatial and temporal extents. Mapping both primary and secondary raw materials requires remote sensing data and mine-specific in-situ information. For these to be overlaid, correlated, and interpreted together, a high degree of spatial and spectral normalization is required. The TL2 processing of satellite inputs ensures that mining sites identified from one source are correctly georeferenced relative to spectral layers derived from another, even when different sensors or acquisition modes are involved. This is also important for secondary raw materials which must be linked back to primary extraction records and geological context. The ARD outputs at TL2 ensure that

time-aligned composites are available for volumetric and compositional tracking, providing the foundational data necessary for the estimation of secondary resource stocks.

In the context of dynamic hazard mapping, addressed in T9.5, the hazard map services rely on continuous monitoring of slope stability, rainfall accumulation, and ground vibration are designed to be updated in near real-time, with the ability to flag emergent risks based on current conditions. This can only happen if each layer in the fusion pipeline is aligned in space and time, and if noise has been sufficiently suppressed. The preprocessing needed here is not only geometrical but also statistical: TL2 must support dynamic range normalization, view angle harmonization, and conversion to reflectance or displacement units depending on the source.

The notion of robustness is particularly important. Many EO services are built around general-purpose algorithms that perform reasonably well under ideal conditions but break down in the face of real-world variability; the ARD framework in TERRAVISION must be able to handle these variations. Scalability is another key concern, as data volumes grow, the ARD system must be able to maintain performance. Finally, configurability is essential because each work package has its own unique tolerances, thresholds, and priorities. A one-size-fits-all ARD product will not meet the needs of every task under WP9-10, the system must allow partners to define the algorithms of their ARD processing pipeline, processing parameters, and receive outputs in formats that suit their tools and models.

Overall, TL2 is considered the baseline of any operational deployment of EO services in the project, serving as a collection of preprocessing functions that are needed for WP9-10. These include cloud masking, pan-sharpening, orthorectification, and sensor-specific corrections across satellite, airborne, and in-situ datasets. All partners involved in WP9-10 implicitly or explicitly depend on these TL2-level ARD outputs for the viability of their pipelines.

3. Framework High level Design

The TERRAVISION project establishes a modular, scalable, and interoperable framework for the processing and analysis of satellite, airborne, and in-situ data tailored to the mining and raw materials sectors. This high-level design addresses the multifaceted challenges of harmonizing and processing heterogeneous Earth Observation (EO) data sources, while ensuring compatibility with the analytical demands of downstream services developed across multiple project work packages.

The updated TerraFusion architecture (figure 1) provides an overview of the software system modules and interfaces supporting the TERRAVISION data flows. It identifies three main data sources:

1. GEP Surface Deformation Mapping data,
2. Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem EO-based data,
3. as well as a pool of EnMAP, PRISMA, DIMAP, HR/VHR Third Party provider data, field samples, in-situ sensor data and weather data

In this context, the TERRAVISION ARD framework is structured into four sequential layers, each responsible for a distinct stage in the EO data lifecycle, from raw ingestion to semantic analysis and interpretation. These layers provide a flexible backbone capable of supporting a wide spectrum of use cases, including spectral analysis, deformation monitoring, object-based change detection, and long-term environmental surveillance.

Figure 1 TerraFusion system architecture and TERRAVISION ARD 4 Layers framework diagrams.

3.1 TERRAVISION Level 1 (TL1)

TERRAVISION Layer 1 represents the entry point of the TERRAVISION pipeline, integrating multi-modal image data from satellite, airborne, and sensor-based sources. This layer ensures the pipeline accommodates the full scope of Remote Sensing assets required for comprehensive raw materials monitoring.

Data types:

- Satellite imagery (e.g. Sentinel-2, EnMAP and PRISMA)
- Airborne imagery (hyperspectral data from flight missions and UAV)
- In-situ sensor data (e.g., temperature, humidity or atmospheric profiles collected from extensimeters and piezometers)

This multimodal capability is directly aligned with requirements from WP9.1 and WP9.2, which need highly detailed spatial and spectral information (e.g., for spectral libraries and InSAR processing). Integrating sensor-level data from the start enables robust downstream fusion and normalization, a necessity especially emphasized in WP9.5 for hazard mapping across sensor types.

3.2 TERRAVISION Level 2 (TL2)

Once data is ingested, TERRAVISION Layer 2 performs a series of essential preprocessing steps aimed at transforming raw imagery into Analysis Ready Data (ARD). This is the most foundational part of the pipeline, where geometric inconsistencies are corrected and atmospheric disturbances such as clouds and shadows are masked. The tasks executed in this layer include:

- **Cloud and Shadow Masking:** this process detects and masks pixels obscured by clouds and their shadows, ensuring cleaner inputs for subsequent analysis. In TERRAVISION, this is done using Machine Learning models trained on both spectral and spatial characteristics of clouds, with performance anchored by the use of ground truth images and cloud and shadow masks. This task is particularly crucial for maintaining data quality in time-sensitive applications like change detection and spectral analysis, where the presence of cloud artifacts would lead to significant inaccuracies.
- **Pan-sharpening:** this process enhances the spatial resolution of multispectral imagery by merging it with high-resolution panchromatic bands. This task will be executed primarily in WP9.3 as part of their super-resolution and mineral mapping workflows, but the TERRAVISION framework will support its integration by allowing pan-sharpened products to be processed and passed through subsequent stages. This ensures that even partner-generated enhancements remain interoperable within the broader pipeline, benefiting tasks that demand high spatial detail, such as object delineation and infrastructure detection.
- **Orthorectification:** this process corrects geometric distortions resulting from terrain relief, sensor orientation, and viewing geometry. In the TERRAVISION pipeline, this is achieved using Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), Rational Polynomial Coefficients

(RPCs), and spatial reference data provided by shapefiles. The output is an orthorectified georeferenced, spatially consistent image that aligns with a common coordinate system. This task is essential for all downstream applications that rely on accurate spatial alignment across time and sensor platforms, including deformation mapping, change detection, and object-based analysis.

The preprocessing tasks in Layer 2 are executed in a logically structured sequence, where each step builds upon the outputs of the previous one. For example, although accurate orthorectification mostly depends on the DEM and the GCPs, taking a cloud-free image as input can improve the ease and reliability of the process, thus making it beneficial to perform cloud and shadow masking beforehand. This stepwise progression ensures that the data becomes increasingly standardized, accurate, and usable as it moves through the pipeline.

At the same time, the TERRAVISION framework remains highly configurable. Users can selectively apply only those preprocessing components that are relevant to their particular workflow, without disrupting the sequential logic of the pipeline. This flexibility is vital given the diverse analytical priorities across project partners. WP9.3, for example, relies on atmospherically corrected, radiometrically stable data for super-resolution modelling and mineral classification. WP9.2 requires precisely georeferenced SAR data aligned with optical imagery for surface deformation analysis. Meanwhile, WP9.5 depends on harmonized, temporally consistent datasets to identify genuine ground changes rather than artifacts introduced by sensor or atmospheric variability. This configurable yet orderly design ensures that the pipeline can adapt to specific project contexts while preserving data integrity and analytic continuity.

3.3 TERRAVISION Level 3 (TL3)

Layer 3 constitutes the analytical core of the TERRAVISION framework.

Most of the Layer 3 input data is coming from the Layer 2 outputs, but also from identified EO-based data such as Surface Deformation maps, or Changes in Stockpile Volumes (cf. Figure 1).

At this stage, pre-processed and harmonized data is transformed into semantically meaningful outputs through a set of dedicated, modular analysis services. These services are also executed sequentially or independently depending on the desired output, and each is designed to consume the products of Layer 2 directly. The major analytical modules include:

- Time Series Analysis, which constructs multi-temporal stacks of imagery to detect gradual changes and long-term trends. This is particularly important for WP9.4, whose work focuses on detecting patterns in material accumulation and land use transitions over extended periods.
- Semantic Captioning, which employs vision-language models to generate human-readable descriptions of EO scenes. This module adds explainability to EO outputs and supports users who require contextual summaries, especially during validation or reporting tasks.

- Object Detection, where trained models identify key features such as stockpiles, mining pits, or infrastructure. For WP9.3 and WP9.5, this enables the delineation of objects that inform mineral mapping and hazard monitoring, respectively.
- Change Detection, which compares multi-temporal images to identify significant transformations. This capability is at the heart of WP9.5's work on landslide and rockslide detection, which relies on object-based analysis of changes over time.
- Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) Classification, which categorizes pixels or segments based on surface type. This service supports regulatory monitoring, environmental impact assessment, and raw material classification tasks across multiple work packages.

These tasks are orchestrated in a pipeline that preserves configurability. Users can activate or bypass specific modules depending on the needs of their use case. The analytical flexibility of this layer is fundamental to supporting partners with highly variable workflows. WP9.1, for example, needs access to reflectance values and metadata indexed by spectral signature; WP9.4 needs automated methods for compositing and anomaly detection across years; and WP9.5 requires configurable parameters to isolate real-world changes from data inconsistencies. The framework's design ensures that each of these requirements can be met within a unified yet adaptable processing environment.

3.4 TERRAVISION Level 4 (TL4)

The final layer of the TERRAVISION pipeline focuses on the synthesis, fusion, and higher-order interpretation of the outputs generated in Layer 3. This stage transforms individual analysis products into coherent, multi-source insights suitable for decision support, reporting, and user-facing applications. Central to this layer is the Information Fusion and Generative Vision Language Models (VLM) module, which integrates data from time series analysis, object detection, semantic captioning, and other services to produce structured outputs such as risk maps, alerts, or descriptive summaries.

This layer directly supports partners who require fused, interpretable outputs. WP9.5's hazard risk profiles can be constructed by integrating change detection results with metadata and historical context, while WP9.4's dashboards can display time series trends alongside semantic annotations. Furthermore, the use of OpenEO interfaces ensures that users can access and orchestrate these services programmatically, embedding TERRAVISION into their existing analytical ecosystems.

4. Framework Implementation

4.1 System architecture

4.1.1 Design goals and principles

The framework is organized into four sequential, well-defined TERRAVISION Layers —TL1 through TL4—each responsible for a distinct stage in the journey from raw sensor data to actionable geospatial products. **TL1 (Ingestion Layer)** ingests and normalizes diverse raw inputs—such as Sentinel-2 satellite datacubes [1], airborne imagery, digital elevation models, etc.—validating file integrity, reprojecting coordinate reference systems, and buffering data into a consistent in-memory format. **TL2 (Pre-processing Layer)** then transforms these raw inputs into analysis-ready data by applying atmospheric corrections, orthorectification using DEMs, cloud and shadow masking, and other similar algorithms [2]. **TL3 (Feature Analysis & Inference Layer)** executes advanced analytical models [3]—semantic segmentation, object detection, and grounding —on the cleansed data, leveraging GPU acceleration to extract features, generate detection outputs, and produce pixel-wise labels. Finally, **TL4 (Fusion Layer)** collates, fuses, and post-processes the TL2 and TL3 results into final deliverables and summary reports outputs. By partitioning the pipeline into these four modular stages, the framework enforces clarity of responsibility, simplifies maintenance, and enables targeted optimization at each step.

Figure 2 Methodology, and principal modules and principles.

Built atop this layered architecture are five interlocking design principles—**modularity**, **configurability**, **extensibility**, **reproducibility**, and **performance**—that together ensure a robust, maintainable, and adaptable system. Modularity enforces strict separation of concerns: each layer implements a uniform interface and lives in its own package, preventing changes in one stage—such as swapping out a cloud-masking algorithm in TL2—from cascading unintended side-effects into others. Developers can therefore evolve, test, and document each module in isolation, shortening feedback loops and reducing integration risk. This modularity also underpins parallel development, allowing teams to work concurrently on different layers or algorithms without code conflicts and accelerating feature delivery.

Configurability complements modularity by exposing every aspect of pipeline behavior through a human-readable JSON schema rather than hard-coded parameters. Users specify inputs, algorithm selections, hyperparameters, and output targets in a single configuration file. A hierarchical defaults-and-overrides mechanism allows global settings—such as the default CUDA device, logging verbosity, or workspace paths—to be defined once, while each algorithm overrides only the parameters it needs. This approach eliminates inline code edits, reduces configuration drift across environments, and empowers end users to reproduce experiments precisely or explore “what-if” scenarios simply by modifying JSON.

Extensibility [4] is realized through a class-registry pattern and plugin directories. Each algorithm registers itself in a central `CLASS_REGISTRY`, mapping a unique key (e.g. "MyCloudMasker") to its implementing class. When the pipeline loader parses the JSON, it dynamically instantiates components based on these keys. To introduce a new detector in TL3, for example, a developer needs only place a properly structured module under “src/main/python/TL3/MyNewDetector/”, implement the required interface, and register it—no modifications to core framework code are necessary. This plugin architecture accommodates third-party enhancements, fosters community-contributed algorithms, and future-proofs the framework against evolving analytical techniques.

Reproducibility permeates every aspect of framework design. All dependencies [5] are managed through a `requirements.txt` file; critical runtime variables—such as GPU device identifiers, file-system paths, and API credentials—reside in a version-controlled `.env` file and are loaded at runtime via `python-dotenv`. By decoupling environment setup from code and tracking every configuration parameter in version control, the framework guarantees that a given pipeline invocation yields identical results regardless of when, where, or by whom it is run.

Performance is the final pillar of the design, ensuring the framework can scale from research prototypes to production deployments. Wherever possible—especially in TL3 inference—compute-intensive operations leverage GPU acceleration via PyTorch [6]. TL1 ingestion employs file readers to mitigate I/O bottlenecks, while TL2 and TL3 algorithms process to maximize GPU utilization. Structured logging and lightweight metrics hooks record per-layer runtimes, data volumes, and success/failure flags, enabling rapid identification of performance hotspots and informing future optimization efforts.

By first delineating the four-layer structure and then applying these five principles, the framework achieves a harmonious balance between clarity, adaptability, and efficiency—providing a solid foundation for all downstream geospatial analyses.

4.1.2 System overview and data flow

Error! Reference source not found. illustrates the high-level block diagram of the framework pipeline. Raw inputs—from multispectral Sentinel-2 tiles and airborne imagery to digital elevation models (DEMs) and ancillary numerical records—enter at the left and progress through four sequential layers (TL1–TL3), each encapsulating a distinct processing stage.

Figure 3. System overview and data-flow UML diagram.

The system is organized into four conceptual layers, each embodied in concrete loader and processor classes that move data from raw files to finished geospatial products. In the Input Layer (TL1), the Airborne and Satellite loaders perform file discovery, integrity and format checks, and memory assembly. Hyperspectral headers are scanned and opened via the Spectral library, while NetCDF datacubes are opened with Xarray. For tiled orthophotos, a reference CRS is inferred from the first file and any mismatched tiles are flagged; rather than warping pixel grids, the loader simply reassigns the CRS metadata in place before merging all tiles into a coarse-resolution mosaic. Elevation rasters (DSM/DTM) and thermal images are likewise read into individual Xarray DataArrays. By centralizing checksumming, CRS reassignment, mosaic creation and array construction in TL1, all downstream components operate on consistently labelled, in-memory arrays without bespoke parsing logic or conditional branches.

Once data has been standardized and loaded in TL1, they flow into the Pre-processing Layer (TL2), where a JSON-driven pipeline of correction modules transforms raw digital numbers into analysis-ready reflectance products. Orthorectification modules apply DEM-based geometric adjustment (using the DEM arrays provided), and cloud and shadow masks are generated via threshold-based classification on the Satellite loader’s SCL band. Each pre-

processor adheres to a common `run(input_data) → output_data` interface, so new correction methods can be introduced simply by adding them to the JSON configuration.

In the Feature Analysis & Inference Layer (TL3), cleaned data is processed on GPU hardware. Semantic segmentation networks assign pixel-level labels, object-detection pipelines produce bounding boxes or instance masks. Because every inference module implements a uniform interface inherited from the base class, multiple models can be composed into ensemble or multi-task workflows without additional integration effort,

Finally, in the Fusion Layer (TL4), all inference results are collated into user-ready deliverables. Segmentation masks and detection outputs are fused into composite overlays. By encapsulating every format and destination behind the same interface, the system can introduce new output targets, whether cloud-native object stores or interactive dashboards—without modifying core analytical code. Throughout all layers, well-defined handoff methods and a plugin-based registry ensure that extensions at any stage can be integrated with minimal friction and zero risk of breaking existing functionality.

4.1.3 TL1 – Ingestion Layer

Ingestion Layer (TL1) functions as the essential gateway between raw sensor data and the analytical framework, providing a consistent, in-memory representation of heterogeneous inputs. At its core, TL1 is defined by a base interface (`TL1_Input`) that prescribes methods for retrieving the assembled “datacube,” generating diagnostic overview images, and accessing auxiliary products such as sun-view angles, digital elevation models, cloud masks, or ground-truth arrays. Concrete implementations—such as the `Airborne` and `Satellite` subclasses—inherit this interface and encapsulate all the logic required to traverse file hierarchies, enforce data integrity checks, and harmonize coordinate systems.

When you instantiate the `Airborne` loader—by giving it your project root, a hyperspectral project prefix (for instance, `sp202402`), and an optional list of flight-line IDs—it immediately:

1. Scans `hyperspectral/hslvTL3` for `.hdr` files matching your project and (if provided) time indices. Each header is opened with the Spectral Python library, converted into `float32` arrays, and split into individual bands. Every band is stored as an `xarray.DataArray` named `<descriptor>_B###` and carries metadata attributes (`project`, `line`, `sensor`, etc.).

Figure 4 Example of spectral image, normalized, extracted from airborne data.

2. Loads all GeoTIFF [7] [8] tiles from images/tiled_ortho, automatically reassigns any mismatched CRS to the reference of the first tile and merges them into one coarse-resolution mosaic via rasterio.merge. It writes out a PNG overview showing tile boundaries and filenames, then reads that PNG back into memory so you can call `get_debug_image()` on it.

Figure 5 Mosaic overview of Canteras mine with tile boundaries and labels. Image extracted from airborne data.

3. Reads LiDAR DSM and DTM files from lidar/dsm and lidar/dtm, respectively. Each GeoTIFF becomes its own DataArray (named DSM_<tile> or DTM_<tile>), sharing the same spatial grid but tagged with its source and filename.

Figure 6 DSM image extracted from airborne data of Canteras mine.

4. Finally, in thermal/ it ingests both absolute thermal (THERMAL_<name>) and relative-temperature (REL_TEMP_<name>) .tif files, storing each as a DataArray aligned to the same (y, x) coordinates.

Figure 7 Example of thermal image extracted from Canteras mine of airborne data

In practice, an TL1 loader can be instantiated and used with just a few lines of code:

```
from TL1.Input import Airborne
```

```

loader = Airborne(
    path="/data/project",
    hslvTL3_project="SiteX",
    time_indices=[1, 2, 3]
)
datacube = loader.get_datacube()
print(datacube)

```

The Satellite loader, designed for multi-temporal NetCDF datacubes, opens the dataset using `xarray.open_dataset` and provides a generic array selector to extract any combination of bands at a given time index [9] [10]. Specialized methods compute sun and view angles from dedicated bands, derive cloud masks using segmentation codes, and expose convenience functions for RGB image extraction or DEM retrieval. Throughout this process, TL1 performs rigorous staging and validation: it checks for missing directories, filters out-of-project files by filename parsing, resamples imagery during mosaicking to balance performance and fidelity, and annotates every variable with coordinate and provenance metadata. The result is a unified `xarray.Dataset` containing spatially and temporally aligned variables, ready for the algorithmic transformations of the Pre-processing Layer. This would be an example of a satellite image:

Figure 8 Satellite image extracted from Canteras NETCDF. Only bands 2, 3 and 4 have been used to represent it as a RGB image.

In the same way that airborne, the Satellite loader can be brought online with a single command and used to inspect both the raw data and diagnostic outputs:

```

from TL1.Input import Satellite

sat_loader = Satellite(

```

```
    datacube_path="/data/project/sentinel_datacube.nc"
)
datacube = sat_loader.get_datacube()
print(datacube)
```

4.1.4 TL2 – Pre-processing

The Pre-processing Layer (TL2) takes the unified xarray.Dataset produced by TL1 and applies domain-specific algorithms to correct, normalize, and enhance the raw inputs before higher-level analysis. Each TL2 algorithm is implemented as a subclass of TL2_Algorithm with a single process_data(input) method that receives the TL1 loader instance, iterates over specified time indices and bands, and returns a list of standardized TL2_result objects containing both debug imagery and the numerical outputs needed to update the datacube.

A prime example is **CloudMasking**: a mosaicing service that leverages binary cloud masks and parameterized, multi-source, multi-date data selection to aggregate cloud-free pixels into a seamless composite. Upon instantiation, CloudMasking reads its list of time indices and RGB (BGR) band triplets, configures its PyTorch Lightning trainer based on the DEVICE environment variable, then in process_data loops over each time index and band set. It retrieves the binary cloud mask, the input image and ground-truth arrays, resizes them to 256×256, normalizes by per-image maximum to avoid division issues, and constructs a LitDIP inpainting model. After training for a few epochs, the inpainted result is resized back to the original resolution, packaged into a composite debug image, and written into the datacube via input.update_datacube(...).

```
from TL2.CloudMasking import CloudMasking

# Initialize cloud-removal on time indices 0 and 1, using sentinel RGB bands
cloud_algo = CloudMasking(
    time_indices=[0, 1],
    rgb_band_names=["B04", "B03", "B02"])
)
results = cloud_algo.process_data(loader) # loader is an TL1_Input subclass instance
```

Another critical Pre-processing step is **Orthorectification**, which corrects geometric distortions by leveraging RPC camera models and a digital elevation model. The Orthorectification class reads the DEM via input.get_dem(), opens a shapefile to extract the image footprint, loads RPC metadata with GDAL, and repairs any malformed entries. It then rescales the input image using a Gaussian filter, optionally invokes an external DEM generator, and calls make_ortho(...) to warp the image onto a common map projection. The resulting orthorectified TIFF is rotated, flipped, and reloaded into memory as a NumPy array. Because full integration with the project's proprietary imagery is still in progress, this implementation logs a warning and uses placeholder paths and parameters.

```
from TL2.Orthorectification import Orthorectification
```

```

# Apply orthorectification to time index 0 and bands 1 and 2
ortho_algo = Orthorectification(
    time_indices=[0],
    band_names=[1, 2]
)
ortho_results = ortho_algo.process_data(loader)
# Note: Orthorectification is work in progress and uses example data paths.

```

Together, these TL2 algorithms ensure that downstream inference stages receive imagery free of clouds, spatially accurate, and normalized for consistent analysis.

4.1.5 TL3 – Analysis/Inference

The Analysis/Inference Layer (TL3) applies trained models and heuristic predictors to the pre-processed datacube, extracting semantic information such as object locations, classifications, and region masks. Each TL3 algorithm subclasses `TL3_Algorithm` and implements a `process_data(input)` method that receives the TL1/TL2-enhanced loader instance, iterates over specified time indices and bands or frames, and returns structured results—either as JSON-style detection lists or as annotated images wrapped in `TL3_result` objects. By decoupling model setup from execution, TL3 ensures that complex deep-learning frameworks or transformer-based pipelines can be initialized once and then invoked efficiently across multiple inputs.

A representative implementation is **ObjectDetectionDetrex**, which integrates the Detrex object-detector (based on a Swin Transformer backbone fine-tuned on COCO) to identify and localize instances in each RGB frame. In its constructor, the class parses a configuration file, loads pretrained weights via a `DetectionCheckpoint`, and wraps the model in a `VisualizationDemo` helper. During `process_data`, it fetches each frame as a NumPy array from the loader, runs the Detrex inference with a confidence threshold of 0.5, and assembles a list of bounding boxes, class IDs, and confidence scores. The final output is returned as a JSON-formatted dictionary:

```

from TL3.ObjectDetection.detrex_ITA.demo.demo import ObjectDetectionDetrex

# Instantiate Detrex-based object detector for frames 0 and 1
det_algo = ObjectDetectionDetrex(
    time_indices=[0, 1],
    rgb_band_names=["B04", "B03", "B02"]
)
detections = det_algo.process_data(loader) # loader is your TL1_Input subclass instance
print(json.dumps(detections, indent=2))

```

Beyond traditional object detection, the **ObjectDetectionGroundedSAM2** algorithm combines open-vocabulary reasoning with the Segment-Anything Model (SAM v2) to produce both box and mask annotations guided by a textual prompt. Its constructor loads Microsoft’s Florence-2 multimodal foundation model alongside a Hierarchical SAM checkpoint, configuring device settings for mixed-precision inference. The `process_data` method applies a tone-mapping to each input image, invokes Florence-2 to propose bounding boxes for a given prompt (e.g., “house”), then feeds those boxes into SAM2 to generate precise masks. Results

are packaged into `FrameResult` objects containing the original image, box-annotated image, mask-annotated image, and a list of `Detection` dataclasses:

```
from TL3.ObjectDetection.grounded_sam2 import ObjectDetectionGroundedSAM2

# Define inference arguments for two frames
args_list = [
    {"time_index": 0},
    {"time_index": 1}
]
sam2_algo = ObjectDetectionGroundedSAM2(args_list)
results = sam2_algo.process_data(loader)

# Each TL3_result contains debug_image (combined visuals) and algorithm_results
# (detection details)
for res in results:
    res.debug_image.show()
    for det in res.algorithm_results:
        print(det.bbox, det.class_id)
```

Together, these TL3 implementations demonstrate how the framework transitions from pixel-level corrections in TL2 to high-level semantic understanding in TL3. By standardizing the interface for model initialization and output formatting, the system accommodates both class-agnostic segmentation and supervised detection models, paving the way for downstream tasks such as change detection, object tracking, or report generation.

4.1.6 TL4 – Fusion Layer

The Fusion Layer (TL4) sits at the apex of the pipeline, translating pre-processed data and semantic inferences into human-readable narratives or replies. Its role is to bridge the gap between numeric results—such as cleaned imagery, detection lists, or segmentation masks—and end-user interactions, whether that be automated report generation, conversational question-answering, or custom visual summaries. TL3 algorithms subclass `TL3_Algorithm` and expose a single `process_data(input)` method that consumes the loader instance (now enriched by TL1–TL3), invokes one or more large-scale vision-language models, and returns textual or structured outputs suitable for downstream consumption.

A concrete example is the **LLaVACustom** adapter, which integrates the LLaVA vision-language assistant to “talk about” each frame. In its constructor, `LLaVACustom` parses command-line or environment settings (model paths, precision flags, device selection, prompt templates) and instantiates an internal `LlavaChat` client. This client loads a pretrained multimodal model into GPU or CPU memory, configures half-precision and `Torch-TF32` where supported, and selects an appropriate conversational template based on the base model (e.g. LLaMA-2 or Mistral). When `process_data` is called, `LLaVACustom` iterates over a list of frame descriptors, uses `input.get_rgb_image(...)` to pull normalized HWC arrays, and feeds them to `LlavaChat.prepare_image()` and `ask()`. The result is a list of strings—each one the model’s description or answer for the corresponding frame—that can be printed, logged, or embedded in a report.

```

from TL3.LLaVACustom import LLaVACustom

# Define which frames to describe, optionally overriding the default prompt
args_list = [
    {"time_index": 0, "airborne_tile": "tile_A", "prompt": "Summarize key features in this image."},
    {"time_index": 1, "airborne_tile": "tile_B"} # will use the default prompt
]

# Instantiate the TL3 adapter and run it
TL3_algo = LLaVACustom(args_list=args_list)
outputs = TL3_algo.process_data(loader) # `loader` is your TL1_Input subclass instance

# Each entry in `outputs` is a text reply from the vision-language model
for reply in outputs:
    print(reply)

```

By encapsulating all model-loading logic, token formatting, and image preprocessing within the LLaVACustom and LlavaChat classes, the Fusion Layer provides a clean, consistent interface for generating final narrative or conversational outputs. This design makes it straightforward to swap in alternative LLMs or vision-language backends in future iterations without altering the upstream data-processing workflow.

4.2 Architecture Modules

4.2.1 Core abstractions and interfaces

At the heart of the pipeline lies a set of abstract base classes that define **exactly** how each stage of processing must behave. By codifying layer-specific responsibilities in four interfaces—TL1_Input, TL2_Algorithm, TL3_Algorithm, and TL3_Algorithm—data ingestion, pre-processing, analysis, and final fusion can all be developed, tested, and replaced independently, without touching the orchestration logic or JSON configuration machinery. In the paragraphs that follow, the representative code snippet for the Level 1 abstraction is introduced, and the responsibilities and intended use of each interface in turn are described.

```

from abc import ABC, abstractmethod
from typing import Any, Tuple, Sequence
import numpy as np

class TL1_Input(ABC):
    @abstractmethod
    def get_debug_image(self) -> np.ndarray: ...
    @abstractmethod
    def get_sun_angles(self, time_index: int) -> Tuple[np.ndarray, np.ndarray]: ...
    @abstractmethod
    def update_datacube(self, time_index: int, band_indices: Sequence[str], new_values: np.ndarray) -> None: ...

```

This minimal snippet illustrates how any concrete **TL1** class must expose methods for visualizing its internal state, retrieving per-pixel geometry, and mutating the underlying data

cube. In practice, a Sentinel-2 handler, an airborne DIMAP loader, or any future data source will implement these methods, guaranteeing that downstream algorithms never need to know where their inputs came from—only that they can call `get_debug_image()`, `get_sun_angles()`, and so on.

The **TL1_Input** abstraction encapsulates **all** data-ingestion responsibilities and establishes a uniform API for accessing imagery, ancillary data, and ground-truth references. A fully featured implementation provides six core operations:

1. **get_debug_image()** returns a mosaic or overview suitable for quick visual inspection.
2. **get_sun_angles(time_index)** and **get_view_angles(time_index)** deliver per-pixel azimuth and zenith matrices for illumination and sensor geometry, respectively.
3. **get_dem(time_index)** retrieves the elevation surface at each pixel, essential for terrain-dependent corrections.
4. **get_cloud_mask(time_index)** produces a binary mask distinguishing clear sky from cloud cover.
5. **get_ground_truth(time_index, band_indices)** fetches labelled reference imagery for supervised methods.
6. **update_datacube(...)** allows in-place modification of any band slice—enabling corrections or synthetic data injections.

By forcing every TL1 subclass to support these operations, raw data handling is decoupled from algorithmic logic: no matter what the source, higher layers can rely on a consistent, type-safe interface.

Building on that foundation, the **TL2_Algorithm** class defines a single **process_data(input: TL1_Input) → List[TL2_result]** method. Each subclass embodies a pre-processing or correction step—be it atmospheric normalization, orthorectification, or cloud masking. The method takes any TL1_Input instance, invokes its accessors (e.g. `get_debug_image()`, `update_datacube()`), applies the transformation, and returns one or more TL2_result objects. Each TL2_result bundles a debug image for logging or visualization and an algorithm-specific payload (e.g. masks, corrected arrays). Crucially, by restricting TL2 implementations to this signature, the pipeline driver script can iterate over a JSON-configured list of algorithms, invoking them in sequence without bespoke wiring for each new pre-processor.

The **TL3_Algorithm** interface mirrors the TL2 design, but targets **feature extraction and inference**. Subclasses implement **process_data(input: TL1_Input) → List[TL3_result]**, performing tasks such as scene classification, semantic segmentation, object detection with Detrex or Grounded-SAM, and change detection. Each run can produce multiple outputs—bounding boxes, class maps, vector layers—wrapped in TL3_result dataclasses alongside a debug visualization. Because TL3 algorithms share the same method name, input type, and return container shape as TL2, the pipeline can load any third-party deep-learning model or custom prototype simply by dropping it into the `src/main/python/TL3/` folder and registering its class name in the configuration registry.

Finally, the **TL3_Algorithm** abstraction defines **process_data(input)** for **information fusion and final output generation**. Here, multi-source artifacts from TL3 (semantic labels, detection

outputs, time-series summaries) are combined to produce consolidated geospatial products—whether that’s a map of land-use change, a fused data cube for GIS ingestion, or prompts to a large-language model for automated reporting. By capping TL3 to a single method, it is straightforward to prototype generative or reasoning approaches without rewriting the pipeline scaffolding.

Together, these four interfaces form a **pipeline contract**: each layer knows only about the operations it must perform and the types it must consume or produce. The pipelines/*.json files merely list class names and parameters—no conditional logic, no imports, and no manual orchestration. The main driver script dynamically instantiates each class via reflection, calls `process_data()`, and persists outputs according to the user’s configuration. This separation of concerns ensures that adding a new algorithm—be it an TL2 cloud corrector, an TL3 segmentation network, or an TL3 fusion module—requires nothing more than subclassing the appropriate base and registering its path in the JSON.

4.2.2 JSON-Driven configuration

In the JSON-driven configuration paradigm, the entirety of the framework multi-stage processing pipeline is defined by a single, self-contained JSON file. This file encapsulates every detail necessary to instantiate and orchestrate the four logical layers—TL1 (data ingestion), TL2 (pre-processing), TL3 (analysis/inference), and TL3 (final output)—without requiring changes to the underlying Python code. At runtime, the `PipelineConfig.from_json()` class method reads the JSON file, validates the presence of mandatory sections (`TL1_input` and `TL3_algorithm`), dynamically imports the corresponding classes from a central registry, and instantiates each component with its specified parameters. This approach ensures that pipelines remain reproducible, versionable, and transparent, since both the pipeline structure and its parameters are captured in human-readable text.

The top-level JSON schema mandates two required objects—`TL1_input` and `TL3_algorithm`—and two optional arrays—`TL2_algorithms` and `TL3_algorithms`. The `TL1_input` object specifies the data ingestion layer by naming the component type (for example, “Satellite” or “Airborne”) and passing its constructor parameters, such as file paths, date ranges, or project identifiers. When `PipelineConfig` parses this object, it looks up the type in its class registry, imports the matching Python module, and constructs the input stage instance using either keyword-argument unpacking (for object-style parameters) or positional argument expansion (for list-based parameters). In the same way, the `TL3_algorithm` object defines the final fusion or reporting step—often a generative model or custom reporting class—ensuring that the last processing stage is also configurable without code changes.

Between ingestion and output, the pipeline may include zero or more pre-processing algorithms (TL2) and inference algorithms (TL3). Each entry in the `TL2_algorithms` array is an object containing a “type” field and a “params” field; these are executed sequentially to perform tasks such as atmospheric correction, cloud masking, pan-sharpening, or orthorectification. By listing components in the desired order, users control the exact sequence of data corrections without touching Python logic. Similarly, the `TL3_algorithms` array lets users specify any number of analysis routines—object detection, change detection,

land-use classification, or semantic captioning. Each algorithm receives the original TL1 input (not the output of TL2) to maintain consistent reference data and can extract features or inferences as needed.

Under the hood, PipelineConfig maintains a CLASS_REGISTRY mapping short, human-friendly names (such as “CloudMasking” or “SemanticCaptioning”) to full Python import paths. When a JSON file names a type, the registry is consulted; if the user has implemented a custom component, they can extend or override the registry by calling PipelineConfig.register(“MyCustomAlg”, “path.to.MyCustomAlg”) before loading the JSON. This mechanism decouples component discovery from code structure, facilitating community contributions and rapid experimentation. In addition, a simple caching layer ensures that classes are imported only once per run, minimizing overhead.

To illustrate, consider the following minimal JSON snippet for a satellite pipeline. It defines a Level-1 ingestion from a NetCDF datacube, four TL2 corrections, three TL3 inference modules, and a custom LLaVA-based TL3 fusion step:

```
{
  "TL1_input": {
    "type": "Satellite",
    "params": {
      "datacube_path": "/datassd/.../s2_TL2a_AOI_2024-03-14_2025-03-14.nc"
    }
  },
  "TL2_algorithms": [
    { "type": "AtmosphericCorrection", "params": { "time_indices": [3], "band_names": ["B02", "B03", "B04"] } },
    { "type": "CloudMasking", "params": { "time_indices": [17], "rgb_band_names": ["B04", "B03", "B02"] } },
    { "type": "PanSharpening", "params": { "time_indices": [3], "band_names": ["B02", "B03", "B04"] } },
    { "type": "Orthorectification", "params": { "time_indices": [3], "band_names": ["B02"] } }
  ],
  "TL3_algorithms": [
    { "type": "ChangeDetection", "params": { "time_indices": [3], "band_names": ["B02", "B03", "B04"] } },
    { "type": "LulcClassification", "params": { "time_indices": [3], "band_names": ["B02", "B03", "B04"] } },
    { "type": "SemanticCaptioning", "params": { "time_indices": [3], "band_names": ["B02", "B03", "B04"] } }
  ],
  "TL3_algorithm": {
    "type": "LLaVACustom",
    "params": [ { "time_index": 3 } ]
  }
}
```

Execution is as simple as:

```
pc = PipelineConfig.from_json("pipelines/satellite_example.json")
```

```
result = pc.run()
```

This two-line invocation loads, validates, instantiates, and executes every stage from TL1 through TL3, returning the final ARD product (and any associated reports) as Python objects.

Adopting JSON configuration brings several best practices. First, config files should live in a dedicated pipelines/ directory under version control, enabling collaborative review and historical tracking. Second, even though JSON does not natively support comments, editors such as VS Code allow “JSON with Comments,” letting practitioners annotate intent or parameter rationales inline. Third, teams should define and run a quick validation script—simply invoking `PipelineConfig.from_dict()` on each JSON file—to catch missing keys or type mismatches before lengthy computations begin. Finally, when multiple pipelines share common parameter blocks, users can employ lightweight templating tools or Python scripts to generate the JSON dynamically, avoiding duplication and reducing maintenance overhead.

4.2.3 Class registry and plugin architecture

In large-scale data-processing frameworks, maintainability and extensibility are paramount. TERRAVISION adopts a plugin-based design centered on a class registry, which serves as a dynamic bridge between configuration and implementation. By decoupling the specification of processing stages from the concrete algorithm classes, the system achieves a high degree of flexibility: users may introduce, modify, or replace processing modules simply by updating the configuration, without altering the core execution logic.

The cornerstone of this mechanism is the `PipelineConfig.CLASS_REGISTRY`, a class-level mapping from string identifiers to module import paths. When a pipeline is instantiated from a JSON file, each declared component—be it an TL1 input handler or an TL3 inference module referred to by its type name. Internally, the pipeline loader invokes the private method `_load_class(type_name)`, which consults the registry to locate the corresponding module path, dynamically imports the module via `importlib`, retrieves the class object by name, and caches it for subsequent use. Caching minimizes repeated import overhead, while clear error messages ensure that any missing or misspelled entries in the registry surface immediately as `KeyError` exceptions, guiding developers toward corrective action.

Flexibility extends beyond lookup: instantiation of algorithm classes accommodates a variety of parameter formats. The static method `_instantiate(Alg, params)` distinguishes between dictionary parameters—passed as keyword arguments—lists of dictionaries—passed as a single positional argument—and other forms that can be iterated—unpacked as positional arguments. This design enables developers to supply simple and complex configurations alike; tailoring constructor calls to the needs of each algorithm without bespoke parsing logic.

Extending the registry is a straightforward, three-step process. First, implement the new algorithm class in its own module, adhering to the base-class interface. For example, one might add a new TL3 detector at `src/main/python/TL3/NewDetector/NewDetector.py`:

```
from base.TL3Algorithm import TL3AlgorithmBase
```

```

class NewDetector(TL3AlgorithmBase):
    def __init__(self, threshold: float = 0.5, **kwargs):
        super().__init__(**kwargs)
        self.threshold = threshold

    def process_data(self, TL1_data):
        detections = perform_custom_detection(TL1_data.images, self.threshold)
        return detections

```

Second, register the class with the registry before pipeline construction:

```

from src.main.python.PipelineConfig import PipelineConfig
PipelineConfig.register(
    "NewDetector",          # registry key
    "TL3.NewDetector.NewDetector" # module path
)

```

Finally, reference the new detector in the JSON configuration under `TL3_algorithms`:

```

{
  "TL3_algorithms": [
    {
      "type": "NewDetector",
      "params": { "threshold": 0.7 }
    }
  ]
}

```

Upon loading this configuration, `PipelineConfig.from_json()` will resolve the `NewDetector` registry entry, import the specified module, instantiate the detector with the supplied threshold, and seamlessly integrate it into the execution pipeline.

This plugin architecture yields several tangible benefits. First, it decouples configuration from implementation, allowing algorithm development and pipeline orchestration to proceed independently. Second, it promotes extensibility: novel processing stages can be introduced without modifying the core loader or executor. Third, it enhances testability: mock or alternative implementations may be registered in place of production algorithms by simply overriding registry entries at runtime. Finally, this approach fosters maintainability, as the registry provides a centralized overview of all available components, and registration calls can be limited to initialization scripts, keeping the pipeline codebase clean and focused on orchestration.

4.2.4 Environment and dependency management

A reproducible and flexible development environment is critical for ensuring that all contributors—across different machines and operating systems—can install and run the TERRAVISION pipeline without friction. To centralize machine-specific settings such as CUDA device indices or cloud credentials, a simple `.env` file located at the project root is used. For instance:

```
# .env
DEVICE=cuda:1
```

At startup, the pipeline invokes the `python-dotenv` library to load these values into `os.environ`, ensuring that modules responsible for atmospheric correction, AI inference, or data I/O automatically honour the user’s preferences. A minimal loader in `src/main/python/main.py` illustrates this approach:

```
from dotenv import load_dotenv
import os

load_dotenv() # Populate environment variables from .env
DEVICE = os.getenv("DEVICE", "cpu")
print(f"→ Using device: {DEVICE}")
```

All additional variables—whether API keys, custom thresholds, or file paths—can be appended to `.env` and consumed via `os.getenv(...)` or `os.environ[...]`, providing a single source of truth for configuration without scattering hard-coded values throughout the codebase.

All project dependencies are maintained in a single `requirements.txt` file located at `src/main/requirements.txt`, rather than being fragmented across multiple files or formats. This file captures both runtime and development libraries with explicit version pins:

```
xarray[complete]
rasterio==1.4.3
scikit-image==0.25.2
pytorch-lightning==2.5.1
spectral==0.24
flash_attn==2.7.4
streamlit==1.43.2
colorama==0.4.6
sentencepiece==0.2.0
peft==0.15.2
python-dotenv==1.1.0
shapley==1.0.3
sardem==0.4.1
gdal==3.8.4
```

After creating and activating a dedicated Conda environment (e.g., `conda create -n TERRAVISION_ard python=3.10 && conda activate TERRAVISION_ard`), users install compiled dependencies such as PyTorch or GDAL via Conda channels and then run a single command:

```
pip install -r src/main/requirements.txt
```

This unified workflow simplifies onboarding, prevents “dependency creep,” and guarantees that every contributor works with the exact same library versions, minimizing “works on my machine” issues.

To integrate third-party repositories—such as `Detrex/Detectron2` or `GroundedSAM2`—while preserving version control and update flexibility, Git submodules are employed. Upon cloning the `TERRAVISION` repository, initialization requires:

```
git submodule init
.git submodule update --recursive
```

When updates are needed (for example, a bugfix in Detrex), one navigates into the submodule directory, checks out the desired commit or tag, and commits the submodule pointer in the main repository. Adding a new module follows the pattern:

```
git submodule add https://github.com/username/ExampleModule.git \
src/main/python/TL3/ObjectDetection/ExampleModule
git commit -m "Add ExampleModule submodule"
```

Submodule references are maintained in the top-level `.gitmodules` file, and CI pipelines must include `--recursive` flags to ensure all code is present during testing and packaging.

By combining a single `.env` file for configuration, a consolidated `requirements.txt` for dependency management, and robust Git submodule practices, the TERRAVISION pipeline achieves a balance of usability, reproducibility, and modularity. Contributors can focus on algorithm development and data analysis rather than environment setup, confident that their code will run reliably across diverse systems.

4.2.5 Testing and validation

In the framework pipeline, testing and validation are integral: every component must include automated unit tests that both confirm its functional behaviour and ensure it adheres to the defined interface. Python's built-in unit test framework is employed to discover and execute tests located under `src/test/python`, ensuring that no code change is merged without having passed the full suite. All tests are invoked via the command:

```
python -m unittest discover -v -s src/test/python
```

Our unit-test modules adhere to a rigorous structure designed for clarity and extensibility. Each test class is named `Test<AlgorithmName>`, for example `TestCloudMasking`, and defines a `setUp` method that (1) loads a minimal JSON pipeline via `PipelineConfig.from_json`, (2) retrieves the `TL1_input` fixture, and (3) constructs any synthetic data—dummy images, masks, or metadata—required to exercise the algorithm under test. If necessary, a `tearDown` method cleans up temporary artifacts or resets global state. Individual test methods, prefixed with `test_`, then exercise specific behaviours: shape consistency, boundary-condition handling, numerical-accuracy assertions against ground truth (using mean squared error thresholds), and proper exception raising when invalid inputs are provided.

To illustrate, consider the `TestCloudMasking` suite, which validates a mock TL2 algorithm responsible for identifying and filling cloudy regions. After the pipeline is instantiated and `process_data` is invoked on the configured algorithm, an assertion is made to ensure that at least one result is produced. For each result, it is verified that the resized cloudy input and its ground-truth counterpart have identical dimensions, and that the spatial shape of the cloud mask matches the first two dimensions of the ground truth. The computation proceeds by:

```
mse = np.mean((ground_truth_resized - inpainted_result) ** 2)
```

and assert that it remains below 0.02, reflecting acceptable reconstruction fidelity. Additional verification is performed to ensure that the masked pixels were indeed modified (i.e., non-zero difference outside the mask) and that unmasked pixels remained essentially unchanged (maximum per-pixel change below 0.11). This combination of structural and numerical assertions guarantees that the algorithm produces both semantically correct and quantitatively reliable outputs.

4.2.6 Extending the code

To accommodate new pre-processing steps without touching the core pipeline, the TERRAVISION framework treats each TL2 algorithm as a self-contained “plugin” that is added via three simple steps: implementation, registration, and configuration. First, you create a new Python package under `src/main/python/TL2/`, for example `MyNewCorrection`, and define a class in `MyNewCorrection.py` that inherits from `TL2_Algorithm` and implements the `process_data` method. Within `process_data`, you retrieve whatever bands or indices you need via the provided input API, perform your correction logic (e.g. thresholding, filtering, cloud masking), then update the datacube in place and return any debug artifacts wrapped in `TL2_result`. For instance:

```
from TL2.TL2_Algorithm import TL2_Algorithm, TL2_result
import numpy as np

class MyNewCorrection(TL2_Algorithm):
    def __init__(self, intensity_threshold: float = 0.5):
        self.threshold = intensity_threshold

    def process_data(self, input) -> List[TL2_result]:
        # Retrieve the NIR band on the first time slice
        arr = input.get_image(0, ["NIR"])
        # Zero-out all values below the threshold
        corrected = np.where(arr < self.threshold, 0, arr)
        # Write the result back into the datacube
        input.update_datacube(0, ["NIR"], corrected)
        # Return a single TL2_result (no debug image in this example)
        return [TL2_result(debug_image=None, algorithm_results=corrected)]
```

Next, you must register the fully qualified import path in the framework’s central registry. In `src/main/python/pipelines/PipelineConfig.py`, simply add:

```
CLASS_REGISTRY["MyNewCorrection"] = "TL2.MyNewCorrection.MyNewCorrection"
```

This explicit mapping guarantees that only reviewed code becomes available to production pipelines, avoiding fragile file-system scans and improving security and maintainability. Finally, to invoke your new module, include it in any JSON configuration under the `TL2_algorithms` array. For example, in `pipelines/satellite_custom.json`:

```
{
  "TL1_input": { "type": "Satellite", "params": { /* ... */ } },
  "TL2_algorithms": [
    {
```

```
"type": "MyNewCorrection",
  "params": { "intensity_threshold": 0.7 }
},
"TL3_algorithms": [ /* ... */ ],
"TL3_algorithm": { /* ... */ }
}
```

At runtime, the pipeline will look up "MyNewCorrection" in CLASS_REGISTRY, import your class, instantiate it with the provided parameters, and chain it seamlessly into the pre-processing layer. By following this pattern—code in its own TL2 subfolder, explicit registration, and JSON-only configuration, you can extend or replace any correction step without modifying core logic, enabling rapid experimentation and clean separation of concerns.

4.2.7 Case study: example pipeline run

This case study details the execution of the satellite_example.json pipeline, converting raw Sentinel2 imagery into Analysis Ready Data (ARD). The JSON configuration, located in pipelines/satellite_example.json, defines a four layer workflow (TL1–TL3). Below is a continuous narrative describing each layer and indicating where to include screenshots of the Streamlit interface or output images.

Pipeline Configuration: The pipeline configuration specifies the datacube path and the chain of processing algorithms. Key sections include:

```
{
  "TL1_input": { "type": "Satellite", "params": { "datacube_path":
"/datassd/.../s2_TL2a_Canteras_..._batch_with_clouds.nc" } },
  "TL2_algorithms": [ /* AtmosphericCorrection, CloudMasking, PanSharpening,
Orthorectification */ ],
  "TL3_algorithms": [ /* ObjectDetectionGroundedSAM2, ChangeDetection,
LulcClassification, SemanticCaptioning */ ],
  "TL3_algorithm": { "type": "LLaVACustom", "params": [{"time_index":3}] }
}
```

Save this JSON as pipelines/satellite_example.json prior to running the pipeline.

Pipeline Execution: Launch the pipeline with:

```
streamlit run src/main/python/main_streamlit.py --server.port 2002
```

The script reads environment variables (e.g., DEVICE from .env), initializes the Streamlit app, and executes the four layers in sequence. When opening the Streamlit, the corresponding pipeline must be selected from the left sidebar:

Figure 9 Streamlit of the framework.

4.2.8 Layer 1: Input Loading

The system ingests the Sentinel-2 NetCDF datacube, validates file paths, and reads metadata. A debug thumbnail (if produced by the input class) is rendered in the Streamlit UI.

Figure 10 Capture the Streamlit panel showing the debug image.

4.2.9 Layer 2: Pre-processing & Corrections

Atmospheric and geometric corrections refine raw data:

- Atmospheric Correction does not apply.
- **Cloud Masking** identifies clouds on the RGB composite at index 17.
- **Pan-Sharpening** does not apply.
- Orthorectification does not apply.

Figure 11 Streamlit displaying the cloud masking algorithm result.

4.2.10 Layer 3: FEATURE Analysis & Inference

AI-driven algorithms extract semantic features:

- Object Detection (Grounded-SAM2): Prompts segment objects.

Figure 12 Object detection in the satellite image.

- Change Detection: Does not apply.
- LULC Classification: Does not apply.
- Semantic Captioning: Does not apply.

4.2.11 Layer 4: Fusion & Final Output

The LLaVACustom module merges segmentations, classification maps, and captions into a consolidated report or GIS artifact.

Figure 13 Result of LLaVACustom.

System diagram, communication interfaces of the different modules, taking into account the local version and OpenEO version.

The ARD Framework will take the input data, being satellite images, airborne images or numerical data from in-situ sensors.

TL2 step refines the satellite images to make them analysis-ready through a sequence of preprocessing steps: Atmospheric Correction, Cloud Masking, Pan Sharpening and Orthorectification (in that order).

Airborne data does not require this preprocessing, since flights will always be in a lower altitude compared to satellites, so there will be no problems with clouds or geometric distortions due to Earth's curvature and atmosphere.

Sensor data processing will be determined once the data is available to be studied.

Every algorithm in TL2 will be optional, so the service providers can determine the level of data-readiness necessary for their tasks.

The cleaned and pre-processed image is passed into TL3, where it can be fed to a series of models, depending on the task: Semantic Captioning, Object Detection, Change Detection, LU/LC Classification and a Visual Language Model.

Finally, the different inputs (satellite, airborne, sensors) and the output from the different steps will be merged into a single data product in TL3.

4.3 TERRAVISION Layer 2 implementation

TERRAVISION Layer 2 (TL2) processing involves applying essential surface-level corrections to raw satellite imagery, transforming it into Analysis Ready Data suitable for a wide range of remote sensing applications. These corrections typically include steps such as cloud masking,

pan-sharpening and orthorectification, each of which plays a crucial role in improving the accuracy and usability of the imagery.

In this framework, TL2 processing is designed to be both modular and systematic. Users have the flexibility to select which TL2 correction tasks to apply, while the system guarantees that the chosen tasks are executed in a predefined, logical sequence. This fixed execution order is critical for ensuring the consistency and integrity of the final output, as certain corrections depend on the successful completion of others. For example, orthorectification, a process that geometrically corrects images to align with real-world coordinates, should logically follow cloud and shadow masking to prevent obstructions from impacting spatial accuracy.

At present, the implemented TL2 pipeline includes two key correction tasks: cloud and shadow masking, and orthorectification. It is important to note that the current pipeline does not apply additional atmospheric or radiometric corrections such as surface reflectance generation, radiometric normalization, or sensor cross-calibration, as input imagery is assumed to be pre-processed to at least that level.

The cloud and shadow masking module identifies and filters out atmospheric disturbances that can obscure ground features, thereby enhancing the clarity and reliability of the imagery. Meanwhile, the orthorectification module corrects for terrain-induced distortions and sensor geometry, ensuring that spatial measurements derived from the images are precise and geospatially accurate.

Together, these TL2 processes significantly enhance the quality of satellite data, making it suitable for downstream tasks such as land cover classification, change detection, and semantic captioning. This architecture not only facilitates rigorous preprocessing but also supports scalability and future extensibility, allowing additional correction modules to be integrated seamlessly as new requirements and algorithms emerge.

Figure 14 TL2 sequential framework diagram.

4.3.1 Cloud and shadow masking

The cloud masking project for satellite imagery begins fundamentally with handling raw Earth observation data in NetCDF format, which is widely used for storing multi-dimensional scientific data. This format is particularly suitable because it can accommodate large arrays of spectral bands captured over multiple timestamps and geographic coordinates. Efficient access to this data is achieved using the Python library *xarray*, which offers a high-level interface to work with labeled, multi-dimensional arrays, making it much easier to query and manipulate datasets compared to raw NetCDF handling.

4.3.2 NetCDF extraction

As an example, Sentinel-2 data is used to perform cloud and shadow masking. The process begins by loading a large dataset that contains multiple spectral bands of Sentinel-2 satellite imagery over a specific area and time span. The dataset path is specified, for example:

```
netcdf_path_with_clouds =  
"/.../TERRAVISION/TERRAVISION_satellite_TL2a/s2_TL2a_Canteras_AOI_2024-03-  
14_2025-03-14_batch.nc"  
ds = xr.open_dataset(netcdf_path_with_clouds)
```

After loading, the dataset (ds) contains various variables corresponding to spectral bands (e.g., B02, B03, B04, etc.), each with spatial dimensions (latitude, longitude) and temporal dimension t. Because satellite images are acquired repeatedly, selecting a specific timestamp is crucial for consistency. A target index is fixed, for instance, indice_t = 17, which corresponds to a specific date "2024-03-15".

For each spectral band, the data is extracted by selecting the slice for the target time. The code to isolate the band at the fixed time and handle missing time dimension gracefully looks like this:

```
if 't' in ds[band].dims:  
    data = ds[band].isel(t=indice_t).squeeze()  
else:  
    data = ds[band].squeeze()
```

This flexibility accounts for bands that may or may not have a temporal dimension.

The spectral bands contain raw reflectance values, often scaled by a factor and clipped to a specific range to avoid outliers. For example, reflectance values are clipped at 10,000 and normalized to the range [0, 1] by dividing by 10,000. This normalization is essential for two reasons: neural networks perform optimally with inputs in a bounded range, and it stabilizes training by avoiding extremely large values. The normalization snippet is:

```
if band.startswith("B") and band[1:].isdigit():  
    data = data.clip(max=10000) / 10000.0  
    data = data.astype("float64")
```

This flexibility accounts for bands that may or may not have a temporal dimension.

The astype("float64") ensures precision during downstream computations, which can be particularly beneficial in sensitive normalization and convolutional operations.

One special band is the Scene Classification Layer (SCL), which labels each pixel with a class such as cloud, vegetation, shadow, or water. Unlike spectral bands, SCL is categorical and thus simply converted to an 8-bit unsigned integer type without normalization:

```
if elif banda == "SCL":  
    data = data.astype("uint8")
```

After these processing steps, each band is saved independently as a .npy file, which is a convenient format for fast disk I/O in numpy-centric pipelines:

```
output_path = os.path.join(output_dir, f"{band}_{objective_date}.npy")
np.save(output_path, data.values)
```

Additionally, a false-color RGB composite image is generated by stacking bands B04 (Red), B03 (Green), and B02 (Blue) to create a human-interpretable visualization:

```
b2 = ds['B02'].isel(t=indice_t).squeeze().clip(max=10000) / 10000.0
b3 = ds['B03'].isel(t=indice_t).squeeze().clip(max=10000) / 10000.0
b4 = ds['B04'].isel(t=indice_t).squeeze().clip(max=10000) / 10000.0

rgb = np.stack([b4.values, b3.values, b2.values], axis=-1).astype("float64")
np.save(os.path.join(output_dir, f"RGB_{objective_date}.npy"), rgb)
```

This step not only supports qualitative assessment but also can be an input for models requiring RGB inputs.

Once the raw .npy arrays are prepared, the challenge arises of converting them into consistent inputs suitable for Deep Learning models. Satellite images often contain invalid pixels represented as NaN (Not a Number), due to sensor errors or atmospheric interference. These NaNs must be removed or replaced, as they can break mathematical operations during training or inference. All NaNs are replaced with zeros using a simple but crucial function:

```
def convert_nans_to_zeros(image):
    return np.nan_to_num(image, nan=0.0)
```

Following NaN cleansing, another challenge is the inconsistent spatial size of satellite images. Original data may come in different aspect ratios and resolutions, which Deep Learning models cannot process directly. This is addressed by performing a center crop on each image to obtain a square patch. The center cropping ensures the most relevant central region of the scene is retained, reducing spatial distortion. The crop code calculates the smallest dimension and extracts the central square region:

```
def crop_center(image):
    h, w = image.shape[:2]
    side = min(h, w)
    start_x = w // 2 - side // 2
    start_y = h // 2 - side // 2
    return image[start_y:start_y + side, start_x:start_x + side]
```

This method ensures the output image is square, a common requirement for Convolutional Neural Networks, which often expect fixed-size square inputs.

After cropping, the images are resized to a standard size of 256x256 pixels using nearest-neighbor interpolation. This resolution is a balanced choice, preserving sufficient detail while allowing reasonable computational performance. Resizing is done carefully to preserve the data range and prevent aliasing artifacts:

```
def resize_image(image, target_size=(256, 256)):
```

```
return resize(image, target_size, order=0, preserve_range=True,
anti_aliasing=False).astype(image.dtype)
```

The use of `order=0` for nearest neighbor is especially important for categorical data, such as masks, because it prevents interpolation artifacts that would blur class boundaries.

After these preprocessing steps (NaN replacement, cropping, and resizing) the resulting arrays are saved back as `.npy` files with a `_corrected.npy` suffix to distinguish them from raw data.

4.3.3 SCL band handling

For the ground truth cloud mask, the process is analogous but tailored to the categorical nature of the SCL band. The raw SCL contains integer codes representing different surface or atmospheric classes. The goal is to create a binary mask indicating cloud presence or absence.

The SCL band assigns a categorical class label to each pixel based on physical and spectral characteristics, using the Sentinel-2 classification scheme. Some of these labels correspond to clouds and their related phenomena, while others indicate clear land, water, or shadow regions. Each class is identified by a specific integer code:

- 0: Missing data
- 1: Saturated or defective pixel
- 2: Topographic casted shadows
- 3: Cloud shadows
- 4: Vegetation
- 5: Not-vegetated
- 6: Water
- 7: Low probability clouds
- 8: Medium probability clouds
- 9 : High probability clouds
- 10: Thin cirrus
- 11: Snow or ice

Out of these, classes 3, 7, 8, and 9 are the ones typically associated with clouds or their immediate effects. Accordingly, when constructing a cloud mask, these values are excluded, as they represent cloudy or contaminated pixels intended for detection and eventual masking. The key to this process is that the binary ground truth mask is not created directly as "1 = cloud" and "0 = no cloud." In fact, it's the inverse:

- 1 (white) for clear pixels (not cloud or shadow)
- 0 (black) for cloud and shadow pixels

```
excluded_values = [3, 7, 8, 9]
excluded_mask = np.isin(data, excluded_values)
inverted_mask = ~excluded_mask
binary = inverted_mask.astype(np.uint8)
```

Here, pixels corresponding to excluded classes are set to zero, while all others are marked one, indicating clear areas. This binary mask becomes the supervised label for model training.

Subsequent center cropping and resizing operations ensure spatial alignment and size compatibility with input images:

```
square = crop_center(binary)
resized = resize_imagen(square)
```

Finally, the binary mask is saved with a `_corrected.npy` suffix for use in training or evaluation.

Together, these preprocessing steps establish a pipeline that carefully converts raw satellite data into structured, normalized, and spatially consistent inputs and labels. Each step is indispensable: normalization stabilizes input distributions; cropping and resizing standardize input shapes. NaN handling prevents computational errors; and mask binarization translates semantic labels into usable ground truth for cloud detection. The modular, reproducible code structure also allows easy adaptation for future datasets or model architectures.

4.3.4 Model implementation

Once the satellite imagery data has been extracted, normalized, and formatted as `.npy` files representing individual spectral bands or masks, the final and most critical stage of the pipeline begins: the Deep Learning model responsible for performing cloud masking. This process, implemented using PyTorch Lightning, revolves around a custom class called LitDIP, derived from DIP (Deep Image Prior) concepts. The code responsible for executing this model is modular and neatly orchestrated, handling dataset assembly, training configuration, and result visualization in a single script.

The model requires three primary components to be loaded before training: the input satellite image with clouds, the corresponding cloud-free ground truth, and the binary cloud mask indicating the presence or absence of clouds. These are loaded using `np.load()` and are assumed to have undergone prior preprocessing through the scripts discussed earlier. Additionally, a placeholder image filled with zeros is created to simulate Sentinel-1 data, which is not used in this context but is presumably expected by the model API:

```
s2_image = np.load('/path/to/s2_image.npy')
s2_mean = np.load('/path/to/ground_truth.npy')
s1_image = np.zeros_like(s2_image)

mask = np.load('/path/to/cloud_mask.npy')
```

These arrays are then provided to the model using two setup methods:

```
my_model = LitDIP()
my_model.set_target([s2_image, s2_mean, s1_image])
my_model.set_mask([mask, np.ones(mask.shape), np.ones(mask.shape)])
```

The `set_target` function establishes the triplet of inputs: the corrupted image (`s2_image`), the ideal ground truth (`s2_mean`), and a filler for multimodal integration. The `set_mask` function accepts three masks, the first of which is the cloud mask targeted for learning; the latter two are identity masks (all ones), regularization masks for secondary losses.

The core training process is orchestrated using PyTorch Lightning's Trainer, a high-level

interface that abstracts away the boilerplate typically required for training loops, device selection, logging, and checkpointing. This greatly simplifies experimentation:

```
trainer = pl.Trainer(  
    max_epochs=4,  
    enable_checkpointing=False,  
    logger=False,  
    accelerator='gpu',  
    devices=2  
)  
trainer.fit(my_model)
```

Using this set of hyperparameters, the model is trained to serve as the basis for inference across all datasets used in the project.

Once training completes, the model's output is retrieved using the `.output()` method, again a custom implementation inside LitDIP. This method is expected to return the reconstructed image or segmentation map:

```
result, _, _ = my_model.output()
```

The script then saves this result, along with the input cloud mask and the original Sentinel-2 image, as PNG files. These visualizations are crucial for qualitative inspection, especially when pixel-level accuracy needs to be validated by a human expert. Each image is rendered using either grayscale or RGB (for Sentinel-2), depending on the data shape and context.

4.3.5 Orthorectification

With the cloud-masked satellite imagery now available, the pipeline advances to one of the most geometrically and geodetically sensitive tasks in remote sensing: orthorectification. This step is essential for transforming a distorted satellite image into a georeferenced, topographically corrected product that aligns precisely with Earth's surface coordinates. The process corrects for both the terrain displacement caused by elevation differences and the viewing geometry imposed by the satellite's sensor. At the heart of this procedure lies a custom module referred to as `Orbview`¹, which orchestrates the entire orthorectification process with a series of tailored tools for reading metadata, computing projection geometry, and integrating digital elevation models (DEMs).

Unlike the cloud masking stage, where model learning played the primary role, the orthorectification stage focuses more on geometric processing, informed by metadata such as Rational Polynomial Coefficients (RPCs) and geospatial footprints encoded in shapefiles. While the overall script remains modular and readable, its operations are highly mathematical and rely on precise geospatial transformations.

The input required by this part of the pipeline includes:

- Cloud-free image, pan-sharpened image (optional)

¹ <https://github.com/mpfaffenberger/orthorectification>

- Shapefile describing the image's geographic footprint
- RPC metadata embedded in the GeoTIFF headers (available for airborne and VHR satellite imagery)
- DEM to simulate terrain corrections (obtained from NASA's Earthdata platform)
- Metadata parsing

The orthorectification begins by loading the shapefile associated with the satellite scene. This shapefile contains the polygonal footprint of the image, i.e., the area on Earth's surface that it covers. The script extracts this geometry using OGR, and converts it into a shapely.geometry.Polygon object for manipulation:

```
file = ogr.Open(shapefile_path)
shape = file.GetLayer(0)
feature = shape.GetFeature(0)
image_footprint = json.loads(feature.ExportToJson())
image_footprint = shapely.geometry.Polygon(image_footprint["geometry"]["coordinates"][0])
```

This footprint is later used to extract geographic bounds, which are necessary for clipping, estimating resolution, and spatial referencing.

Parallel to this, the image is loaded with GDAL to extract RPC metadata, which defines the relationship between image pixels and ground coordinates. RPCs are critical because they approximate the satellite's sensor model and allow one to simulate how the image was projected from the 3D terrain onto the 2D sensor:

```
orbview_dataset = gdal.Open(image_path)
rpc_dict = orbview_dataset.GetMetadata_Dict("RPC")
rpc_dict_repaired = {key: re.sub("[^0-9]\-\.\sE]", "", value) for key, value in rpc_dict.items()}
```

The RPC metadata may contain noise or formatting issues (e.g., stray characters from encoding). The script addresses this with regular expressions to sanitize all entries, a vital step, since downstream geometric computations depend on numeric precision. It also augments the dictionary with min/max latitude and longitude, derived directly from the shapefile polygon:

```
rpc_dict_repaired["MIN_LONG"] = min(lons)
rpc_dict_repaired["MAX_LONG"] = max(lons)
rpc_dict_repaired["MIN_LAT"] = min(lats)
rpc_dict_repaired["MAX_LAT"] = max(lats)
```

The cleaned dictionary is then unpacked using OrbView's helper. This step interprets the polynomial coefficients and prepares them for use in downstream coordinate transformations.

At this point, the image data is read into memory and converted to a format suitable for visualization and projection. Since this is often a multispectral image, the data is averaged across channels to create a single grayscale array that simplifies projection:

```
pixel_data = orbview_dataset.ReadAsArray()
single_channel = pixel_data.mean(axis=0)
```

```
rescaled_img = gaussian_rescale(single_channel, bitness=11).astype(np.uint8)
```

Here, `gaussian_rescale` (from `orbview.scaling_tools`) normalizes the image intensities to an 8-bit scale, compensating for radiometric inconsistencies and preparing the image for better contrast in the orthorectified result.

A preliminary georeferenced image is then saved with rough estimates of resolution (ground sample distance, or GSD) and corner coordinates, again based on metadata and assumptions. This "pre-orthorectified" version is not geometrically corrected but allows for quick visual confirmation that data and metadata align.

4.3.6 DEM Integration

Orthorectification fundamentally relies on a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) to correct for parallax and terrain displacement, distortions introduced by the Earth's varying surface height when observed from an orbital sensor. Ideally, for precise results, the DEM should match the spatial resolution, geographic coverage, and acquisition date of the satellite image. However, at this stage of the pipeline, a dedicated DEM is not yet available for testing. As a result, the system uses a placeholder DEM, generated automatically on-the-fly using the `createdem` command-line tool from the `sardem` library.

```
subprocess.run(['createdem', '11', '49', '2', '2', '--data-source', 'NASA', '--output',  
output_dem_path], check=True)
```

This command instructs the utility to:

- Define a bounding box via center coordinates (11, 49) and box size (2, 2 degrees)
- Specify a data source from which to fetch the elevation data
- Write the output to a DEM file (`elevation.dem`) for use in terrain correction.

The `--data-source` argument is flexible. While NASA often refers to Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) or ASTER Global DEM datasets, this can be replaced with AWS, ESA, or other open-access repositories if needed.

Once the DEM is created, it's read back into memory using GDAL:

```
dem_ds = gdal.Open(output_dem_path)  
raw_dem_data = dem_ds.ReadAsArray()  
dem_geo_t = dem_ds.GetGeoTransform()
```

4.3.7 Orthorectifying process

The core orthorectification step is performed by the `make_ortho` function from the `orbview.ortho_tools` module. This function essentially transforms the raw satellite image into a geometrically corrected, map-accurate image by accounting for terrain elevation and sensor geometry. It does so by creating a new grid of geographic coordinates within the specified bounding box and projecting each of these points back into the original image space.

First, the function generates evenly spaced longitude and latitude coordinates to define the output grid:

```
cols = np.linspace(x1, x2, width)
height = int(abs(y1 - y2) / gsd)
rows = np.linspace(y1, y2, height)
```

Here, the ground sampling distance (gsd) is calculated as the distance between adjacent longitude samples, setting the spatial resolution of the output image in degrees per pixel.

For each geographic coordinate pair (lon, lat) in this grid, the function retrieves the corresponding elevation by interpolating from the DEM:

```
dem_x = int((lon - dem_geot[0]) / dem_geot[1])
dem_y = int((lat - dem_geot[3]) / dem_geot[5])
altitude = linear_interp(dem_x, dem_y, dem.reshape(-1), dem.shape[1])
```

This elevation is critical for correcting terrain-induced distortions in the image.

Using the RPC model, the function maps the geographic coordinate and elevation back into image pixel coordinates. Because these coordinates may not exactly match pixel centers, linear interpolation is used to estimate pixel intensity values smoothly:

```
x, y = lon_lat_alt_to_xy(lon, lat, altitude, rpcs)
result = linear_interp(x, y, source.reshape(-1), source.shape[1])
```

This interpolation improves the visual quality and positional accuracy of the output.

Points that fall outside the bounds of the source image are skipped, avoiding invalid pixel reads.

After processing all coordinates, the flat array of pixel values is reshaped and transposed to form the final 2D orthorectified image:

```
return ortho.reshape(width, height).transpose(), gsd, x1, y1
```

The function returns this corrected image along with the ground sampling distance and upper-left coordinates, providing the spatial context needed for georeferencing.

In this way, `make_ortho` combines DEM-based elevation correction, inverse RPC projection, and interpolation into a comprehensive loop that produces an orthorectified image aligned to geographic coordinates, ready for accurate mapping and further analysis.

Finally, before the final save, the image is rotated and flipped to ensure its orientation matches expected north-up, east-right standards — correcting for quirks in the projection model.

4.4 Utilities Implemented in the Framework Version 1

4.4.1 Utilities for Sentinel-2 data

The process of downloading satellite data from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE) using OpenEO for various mining sites under the TERRAVISION project represents a crucial step in delivering harmonized, Analysis Ready Data (ARD) to service providers. These providers, who will be designing applications for environmental monitoring, mineral exploration, or automated compliance reporting, require consistent and well-documented inputs to ensure downstream tools function effectively. The setup developed ensures not only robustness in data acquisition but also high transparency in processing levels, metadata schemas, and semantic annotation practices, thereby allowing smooth system integration for any TERRAVISION demonstrator.

At the core of this pipeline is the use of Sentinel-2 Level 2A (L2A) imagery, a product which includes bottom-of-atmosphere reflectance values corrected for atmospheric effects. Sentinel-2 L2A data is particularly well-suited for monitoring surface phenomena like vegetation changes, water body fluctuations, or mineralogical variations, making it ideal for applications in mining contexts. CDSE, as the hosting and distribution platform of Copernicus data, provides a rich archive of Sentinel-2 datasets which can be accessed through standardized APIs. It acts as a federated node for the distribution of open Earth Observation data to support EU-wide initiatives in sustainability, environmental policy, and industrial innovation.

To streamline access to this data in a scalable and developer-friendly manner, the project relies on OpenEO, an open API standard that allows users to communicate with various Earth Observation backends through a unified interface. OpenEO abstracts the complexity of interacting with different data providers by providing a common Python (and other language) client library. In the current TERRAVISION setup, the OpenEO backend of CDSE, hosted at openeofed.dataspace.copernicus.eu, is employed. This allows for streamlined authentication via OpenID Connect and facilitates a uniform and reproducible approach to querying, processing, and downloading satellite imagery.

The framework ensures a secure connection to the CDSE backend using OpenEO's authentication, handled through a standard OIDC flow, ensuring proper access control and data handling. Once connected, the satellite imagery is loaded, specifically targeting the "SENTINEL2_L2A" collection. This method allows specification of both temporal and spatial extents, enabling the precise targeting of mine locations for data extraction. These locations are defined using polygon geometries stored in ESRI Shapefiles and parsed using GeoPandas. The geometries from the shapefiles are then converted into a format that OpenEO can consume, creating JSON-style geometry descriptors. As for the time of interest, the framework is configured to download data covering the most recent year (March 2024 – April 2025); however, this time window can be flexibly extended if historical analysis or longer baselines are required. Each download is performed as a batch job using the OpenEO Python API. This ensures that data is processed on the backend infrastructure of CDSE, taking advantage of their computational resources and avoiding the need to perform heavy lifting locally.

The selection of mining sites is composed of three main datasets: Canteras (quarries), Tharsis, and Terna Mag. These are read and concatenated into a single GeoDataFrame, preserving

coordinate reference system integrity throughout. This unification facilitates scalable processing by ensuring a consistent structure across all sites. Each site is annotated with a data acquisition interval strategy—either 'monthly' or 'yearly'—based primarily on the site's spatial characteristics and operational constraints. Sites such as Canteras, La Zarza, and San Telmo are designated for yearly downloads, whereas Tharsis and Terna Mag are processed using monthly intervals. This differentiation is not only a matter of temporal resolution but also a practical solution to handle the larger spatial extent of certain mines. For extensive areas like Tharsis and Terna Mag, retrieving a full year's worth of Sentinel-2 data in a single batch would exceed backend processing or storage capabilities, making segmented monthly retrievals more manageable and reliable. This setup allows the system to maintain a balance between data volume, processing feasibility, and the analytical needs of downstream services.

One of the critical components of the download process involves cloud masking. Sentinel-2 L2A provides a Scene Classification Layer (SCL), which encodes pixel-level metadata such as cloud presence, shadow, snow, and vegetation. The workflow includes a custom OpenEO process applied on the SCL band. This mask is constructed using two kernel sizes for morphological dilation, and it excludes pixels labelled with certain SCL classes that are known to degrade data quality (e.g., dense clouds, cirrus, or shadows). Additionally, an erosion kernel is applied to minimize false positives and edge effects. The final cloud mask is applied to the data cube, alongside a polygon mask to spatially constrain the results to each mine's area of interest. This dual masking ensures the final datasets are both spatially and spectrally clean, minimizing post-processing burdens for the end users.

Two datasets are downloaded for each time interval: one with cloud masking and one without. The cloud-masked version is suitable for most visualization and change detection tasks where precision is paramount. The unmasked version retains all spectral content, including obscured pixels, and may be useful in algorithms that apply their own cloud filtering or uncertainty quantification.

The final output of each data acquisition process is exported in the NetCDF (Network Common Data Form) format, using the .nc file extension. This format is a widely adopted standard for the storage of multi-dimensional scientific data, making it particularly well-suited for EO imagery, which inherently spans multiple axes such as time, space (latitude and longitude), and spectral bands. In the TERRAVISION workflow, NetCDF provides a structured, self-describing container that encapsulates not only the pixel values of the Sentinel-2 L2A reflectance data but also essential metadata. This includes coordinate reference information, temporal coverage, processing history, band names, and quality flags. Such comprehensive internal documentation ensures that the files are immediately interpretable by a wide range of scientific and operational tools, eliminating the need for auxiliary sidecar files or manual metadata parsing. Moreover, NetCDF's compatibility with cloud-native geospatial libraries, such as Xarray, GDAL, and Rasterio, enables seamless integration into downstream analytics and visualization platforms.

Another key advantage of using NetCDF in the TERRAVISION context is its support for compression, chunking, and sub-setting features that are vital when working with large EO datasets. For instance, NetCDF files can be compressed to reduce storage footprint without

compromising data integrity, and they can be read in parallel or in segments, allowing applications to efficiently extract only the required subset of information. This is particularly beneficial when service providers develop dashboards or decision-support tools that need to load time series over a specific site, or retrieve only a few bands relevant to a particular index (e.g., NDVI or NBR). In addition, the adoption of NetCDF aligns with interoperability goals; it is a cornerstone format in the climate and remote sensing communities and adheres to conventions like CF (Climate and Forecast) metadata standards. This consistency supports integration not only within TERRAVISION but also with external data ecosystems and open-data repositories. As a result, service providers can confidently ingest these ARD products into their operational pipelines, knowing that they are built on robust, transparent, and standards-based foundations.

Working with the NetCDF files produced in the TERRAVISION pipeline is streamlined and highly efficient thanks to the use of Xarray, a powerful Python library designed for handling multi-dimensional labelled arrays. Xarray is particularly well-suited for EO data because it treats dimensions such as time, latitude, longitude, and spectral bands as first-class objects, enabling intuitive indexing, selection, and manipulation. When a NetCDF file is opened it automatically parses the metadata and organizes the data into an accessible Dataset structure, where each variable (e.g., a reflectance band or quality mask) is aligned along shared dimensions. This means that service providers can immediately begin analyzing the imagery without needing to write complex parsers or preprocessors. Common operations—such as calculating vegetation indices, resampling temporal data, or filtering based on quality flags—can be performed with concise, readable syntax. Moreover, Xarray integrates seamlessly with other scientific libraries like Dask for out-of-core computation, Matplotlib and Holoviews for visualization, and Pandas for tabular analysis. This ecosystem allows providers to build scalable, interactive applications directly on top of the NetCDF data, ensuring a high degree of analytical flexibility while preserving performance and reproducibility.

Throughout the process, informative logging is employed using Python's logging module. This provides traceable logs of which datasets were downloaded, when, and into which local path. This is crucial for long-term maintenance, error auditing, and performance diagnostics. Furthermore, the use of Xarray is implied in the downstream usage context, as NetCDF files are typically ingested using Xarray's robust multi-dimensional array structures. This allows service providers to seamlessly integrate satellite datasets into their dashboards or algorithms using simple Pythonic commands.

The overall performance of this pipeline is heavily influenced by the network throughput, CDSE backend load, and spatial size of the requested AOIs. Monthly jobs typically execute faster and are easier to monitor individually, but they may introduce overhead due to the higher frequency of job submissions and file handling. Conversely, yearly jobs offer efficiency in batch size but are more susceptible to failure due to their extended runtime. There is also the consideration of quota limitations and backend processing queues, which can introduce delays during peak demand periods. These performance dynamics must be understood by service providers to ensure that expectations around delivery timelines and update cycles are realistic.

Challenges encountered in this process include inconsistent geometric metadata in shapefiles, which may require reprojection or cleaning before they can be used reliably. Another challenge is the harmonization of cloud masking across different atmospheric conditions. Since SCL quality can vary by location and acquisition date, the mask parameters used may require periodic validation. A further complication is the handling of edge effects near the boundary of the AOIs, which can introduce striping artifacts or partial coverage in certain images. Ensuring that data is correctly aligned with the intended region requires careful attention to the spatial reference system and resolution configuration.

From an integration standpoint, the Sentinel-2 data obtained via this workflow is exceptionally suited for downstream applications, once it has been processed with the ARD framework. The semantic consistency of the data—guaranteed by fixed band names, time dimensions, and metadata fields—facilitates ingestion into standardized pipelines. For example, environmental monitoring dashboards can ingest the clean, masked datasets to visualize NDVI, water indices, or surface reflectance changes. Exploration decision-support tools can use the full-spectrum unmasked data to run mineralogical classification or anomaly detection algorithms. Reporting pipelines can rely on the metadata consistency to generate compliance maps or habitat impact assessments with minimal manual intervention.

The emphasis on transparency and documentation throughout the pipeline ensures that every dataset is accompanied by clearly defined processing parameters, spatial extents, and time intervals. This visibility is critical for reproducibility, as it allows any result derived from the data to be traced back to its origin. By relying solely on OpenEO and CDSE, the pipeline remains lightweight and highly maintainable. The absence of proprietary tools or complex orchestration frameworks ensures that the approach can be replicated across other domains or regions with minimal modification. This aligns well with the open, collaborative philosophy of the TERRAVISION project, which aims to democratize access to advanced geospatial intelligence through modular, well-documented, and standards-compliant components.

In summary, the satellite data download strategy implemented for the TERRAVISION mining demonstrators via OpenEO and CDSE provides a robust, transparent, and well-annotated data stream suitable for immediate use by value-added service providers. With clear time segmentation, cloud-aware filtering, standardized metadata, and strong alignment to backend infrastructure, this system offers a scalable blueprint for ARD provisioning. While certain challenges persist—chiefly around geometry standardization, cloud classification reliability, and backend latency—the overall structure ensures high usability and seamless integration across the TERRAVISION ecosystem.

4.4.2 Utilities for EnMAP data

EnMAP (Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program) is a hyperspectral satellite mission designed to provide high-quality Earth observation data for environmental monitoring and analysis. It captures image data in more than 200 spectral bands ranging from the visible to the shortwave infrared, enabling detailed assessments of land surface composition, vegetation health, soil properties, and mineral resources. Its high spectral resolution and moderate spatial resolution are optimized for scientific applications that require accurate

spectral information, particularly in the fields of agriculture, forestry, geology, and water quality analysis. EnMAP is known for its rigorous calibration and validation protocols, ensuring data consistency and reliability across time and space.

Incorporating EnMAP data processing pipelines into the framework is necessary to ensure seamless integration with existing EO datasets. Future development efforts should focus on enabling automated ingestion, preprocessing, and co-registration of these datasets within the analytical environment.

4.4.3 Utilities for PRISMA data

PRISMA (PRecursore IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa), is a hyperspectral satellite mission operated by the Italian Space Agency (ASI). It collects data across the VNIR (Visible and Near Infrared) and SWIR (Short-Wave Infrared) ranges, with a similar application focus to EnMAP. In the context of TERRAVISION, PRISMA has been selected as a complementary source of EO data for mining site monitoring, specifically due to the availability of cloud-free imagery that coincides temporally with Sentinel-2 acquisitions. This temporal proximity facilitates co-registration, making PRISMA data suitable for integration with other multispectral datasets.

However, PRISMA data is known to have a significant geolocation error, often exceeding 200 meters, which necessitates careful geometric correction to ensure spatial accuracy. This correction involves co-registering the PRISMA imagery with high-precision datasets like Sentinel-2. In addition to geometric adjustments, PRISMA data must undergo several preprocessing steps before being suitable for analysis. These include the removal of defective bands—either flagged as invalid in metadata or characterized by over 90% zero values—as well as the exclusion of bands affected by strong water vapour absorption. Radiometric calibration is also required to convert the raw digital numbers into physically meaningful reflectance values. Subsequently, the VNIR and SWIR data cubes must be assembled into a single continuous hyperspectral cube for seamless analysis.

Incorporating PRISMA data processing pipelines into the framework is necessary to ensure seamless integration with existing EO datasets. Future development efforts should focus on enabling automated ingestion, preprocessing, and co-registration of these datasets within the analytical environment.

4.4.4 Utilities for Airborne data

The airborne data provided by DIMAP for the TERRAVISION project spans multiple sensor modalities, including LiDAR, hyperspectral, thermal, and RGB imaging. Each modality follows a specific data processing pipeline and is delivered in standardized formats designed to ensure interoperability and validity. The files are structured to include both the final products and the intermediate or supporting datasets, providing both immediate usability and traceability for further refinement.

The LiDAR data involves the integration of raw SDF files with detailed aircraft trajectory data, calibration matrices, and system-specific corrections. Then, a waveform rectification export is performed, and Digital Terrain Models (DTMs) and Digital Surface Models (DSMs) are derived

at 0.5m, 1m, and 2m resolutions, provided in GeoTIFF format. The point clouds themselves are provided as LAS files in 1km x 1km tiles and organized by flightline for unclassified but processed datasets. The corresponding file structure for the LiDAR data includes folders such as “dsm”, “dtm”, “las”, and “stripalign”. Product files include .las for point clouds and .tif for DSM/DTM imagery, supported by projection (.prj) and coordinate (.tfw) metadata files. This structure allows seamless integration with GIS software and ensures consistency across spatial analyses.

RGB orthophoto imagery constitutes another core component of the dataset which ensures radiometric corrections, photogrammetric processing and alignment of imagery are applied. The orthomosaic is generated using a Lidar-derived DTM as a reference. The resulting products include tiled TIFF orthophotos and compressed full-resolution mosaics in ECW format. Supporting metadata is provided through .xml, .eww, .prj, .tfw, and .txt files.

Thermal data is processed into temperature-calibrated maps. Initially imported in TIFF format, the images undergo calibration to convert raw DN values to degrees Celsius. The orthomosaic is then generated per flightline due to machine limitations, with pixel resolutions around 0.75 meters. To enhance usability, the dataset includes full thermal maps and differential temperature signals, reflecting environmental variability across capture times. Deliverables include TIFF mosaics, supported by coordinate and projection files, and RAR archives containing individual unmosaicked images.

The hyperspectral dataset is among the richest in spectral resolution, with VNIR and SWIR data captured using Hypspx sensors. Processing includes conversion from raw data to radiance using, georectification of radiance and atmospheric correction. The final product includes two levels of files: hslvl2 (georectified) and hslvl3 (atmospherically corrected). These are stored in Band Sequential (BSQ) format with accompanying header files (.hdr). Additional supporting files include dark dense vegetation indices (_ddv.bsq), visibility indices (_visindex.bsq), and water vapor maps (_wv.bsq)

A unique challenge addressed during processing was the VNIR/SWIR “detector jump”, a spectral discontinuity at the junction of the two sensor ranges. This was mitigated using pan-sharpening, band stacking, and offset ratio correction through ENVI’s Band Math functions. Although the spectral alignment across the full 409-band combined dataset was improved, complete accuracy still depends on external ASD (Analytical Spectral Devices) measurements, which were not included in this processing phase.

All processed data, amounting to over 5 TB in total, is hosted on an FTP server structured by project area (sp202401 for Tharsis and sp202402 for Canteras). Within each project, data is further segmented into modality-specific folders (hyperspectral, images, lidar, thermal), each adhering to a strict file structure and naming convention.

Meter imágenes de los datos de avión de las minas

5. Alpha-version Algorithms Theoretical description

5.1 Algorithm 1 Cloud Masking

5.1.1 Introduction

Cloud masking is the process of identifying and removing clouds, as well as the shadows they cast, from satellite imagery. This is an essential step for producing Analysis Ready Data (ARD) since clouds and their shadows can obscure important surface features and introduce significant noise into Remote Sensing data, making it difficult to accurately monitor land cover, vegetation or water bodies (Laszewski & Gu, 2023).

Cloud masking typically involves the use of algorithms that analyze various spectral bands, especially those in the visible and infrared ranges, to distinguish clouds and shadows from other surface elements. These algorithms may incorporate thresholds, machine learning techniques, or multi-temporal analysis to improve accuracy. In some cases, auxiliary data such as solar angle or thermal infrared information is also used to enhance detection.

By removing or flagging these obstructions, cloud masking ensures that subsequent analyses such as orthorectification, pan-sharpening or change detection are based on clear, unobstructed views of the Earth's surface. This preprocessing step is particularly important in regions with frequent cloud cover, where the accumulation of high-quality, cloud-free observations over time is crucial for reliable environmental monitoring and decision-making.

5.1.2 Specific needs

Not all of the satellite or aerial data collected from the mining areas require cloud masking or similar preprocessing steps. In some cases, the data is already corrected, or the presence of clouds is negligible or non-existent. The following datasets are examples where additional cloud masking is generally unnecessary:

- DIMAP Flight Data: These images are captured by airborne sensors mounted on aircraft flying at relatively low altitudes, typically below the cloud layer, and as a result, clouds are completely absent.
- Sentinel-2 Level-2A (TL2A) Products: these are surface reflectance products derived from Level-1C (TL1C) top-of-atmosphere data. As part of the Level-2A processing, an automated cloud detection and masking algorithm (such as Sen2Cor) is applied, which identifies and flags cloud-covered pixels and their associated shadows.

In contrast to these pre-processed or cloud-free datasets, certain other sources still require cloud masking to ensure high-quality ARD. Specifically:

- Sentinel-2 Level-1C (TL1C): this level provides TOA reflectance, and while it contains metadata useful for cloud assessment, it does not include cloud-masked surface

reflectance. Atmospheric correction and cloud masking must be applied separately to derive ARD.

- EnMAP: it provides high-resolution hyperspectral imagery, but its raw data is delivered at TOA level. For consistent, cloud-free surface analysis, one must perform cloud detection and atmospheric correction.
- PRISMA: similar to EnMAP, PRISMA delivers TOA hyperspectral imagery with rich spectral information, but it lacks built-in cloud masking, and therefore requires additional preprocessing to filter out cloud-contaminated observations.

These datasets typically contain top-of-atmosphere reflectance and do not include any form of atmospheric or cloud correction by default.

5.1.3 SCR-DIP

For the cloud masking task the Satellite Cloud Removal DIP (SCR-DIP) (Czerkawski et al., 2022) model has been adapted and implemented.

Github - <https://github.com/strath-ai/satellite-cloud-removal-dip> (Apache-2.0 license)

5.1.4 Model architecture

This method is based on the concept of Deep Image Prior (DIP) (Ulyanov et al., 2020), an innovative approach in image reconstruction that exploits the inherent structure of Convolutional Neural Networks (O’Shea & Nash, 2015) to perform image restoration without requiring any prior training on large datasets.

Figure 15 DIP Image Space visualization. (Ulyanov et al., 2020)

Unlike traditional methods that rely on external datasets to learn image statistics, Deep Image Prior leverages the implicit regularization encoded in the architecture of an untrained Convolutional Neural Network. By fitting the network to a single degraded image using a fixed random input, the optimization process tends to favour natural image structures over noise or artifacts. This property arises from the convolutional architecture's strong inductive bias toward spatial coherence and multi-scale structure, making DIP particularly effective for inverse problems such as denoising, super-resolution and inpainting (Zhang et al., 2022).

Figure 16 Denoising of an image using Deep Image Prior.²

Figure 17 Inpainting of an image using Deep Image Prior.³

SCR-DIP applies this principle to cloud removal by treating cloud-covered regions in satellite images as inpainting areas. Instead of relying on externally trained models, which may struggle to generalize across varying geographic regions and seasons, SRC-DIP optimizes the network specifically for each individual image. Feeding a random noise tensor into the CNN, it iteratively reconstructs the cloud-obscured regions by matching the surrounding cloud-free areas, producing a visually coherent reconstruction without requiring labelled data.

² <https://medium.com/data-science/deep-image-prior-in-pytorch-e6edf666a480>

³ <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/computer-science/articles/10.3389/fcomp.2024.1478233/full>

The structure presents a variety of synthesis modes that define how the model incorporates additional information to guide the inpainting process. These are divided primarily into direct and stacked architectures:

- The basic DIP model (direct mode) uses only the information from the non-cloudy regions of a single image, overfitting the network to reconstruct the obscured parts. This mode is simple but limited in effectiveness when large areas are cloud-covered.
- To improve reconstruction, the model extends to stacked modes, which integrate auxiliary data, either from different times (multi-temporal), different sensors (multi-source), or both. These modes enhance the model's ability to infer plausible textures and structures in cloud-covered regions. For example, the multi-temporal approach stacks historical clear-sky images of the same region, while the multi-source approach brings in radar data (e.g., Sentinel-1 SAR) unaffected by clouds. The most powerful is the multi-source multi-temporal (MS-MT) mode, combining both types of additional input.

Figure 18 Diagrams of synthesis modes. (Czerkawski et al., 2022).

Each synthesis mode modifies the input data structure but still adheres to the internal learning paradigm, no external training on large datasets is needed. Instead, the model is optimized per-image, using the specific instance's structure and any supplementary data to guide reconstruction.

Figure 19 Comparison of DIP-based synthesis approaches. (Czerkawski et al., 2022)

These modes are evaluated both quantitatively and qualitatively. The results show that stacked modes, especially those including temporal support, outperform the basic DIP approach, achieving higher structural similarity and lower error in inpainted regions.

5.1.5 Inputs needed

To generate a corrected, cloud-free image using the SCR-DIP model, several types of input data are required:

- Raw Image: this is the cloud-affected satellite image that serves as the primary input. It contains the Area Of Interest with partial or full cloud coverage that needs to be removed or reconstructed.
- Ground Truth Image: this is a cloud-free reference image of the same geographic location, captured at a different time. It provides structural and spectral information that the model uses to infer the missing or obscured content during the inpainting process.
- Cloud and Shadow Masks: these are binary masks used to identify which pixels in the raw image are obscured by clouds or their shadows (Wright et al., 2024). Each pixel in these masks indicates whether it belongs to a cloud-covered, shadow-covered, or clear region.

The original SCR-DIP project provides a satellite image example of cropland partially covered by clouds, accompanied by the corresponding ground truth as well as shadow and cloud masks. These masks can be combined to accurately identify and reconstruct the cloud-covered areas, resulting in the predicted inpainted regions reconstruction.

Figure 20 Cloud masking example using SCR-DIP.⁴

5.2 Algorithm 2 Orthorectification

5.2.1 Introduction

Orthorectification is the process of geometrically correcting satellite or aerial imagery to remove distortions caused by terrain elevation, sensor tilt, and the curvature of the Earth (Boccardo et al., 2004). This correction transforms the image into a uniform scale, ensuring that the spatial representation accurately reflects real-world geography. As a result, features such as roads, buildings, mountains and land boundaries appear in their true positions, making orthorectified images suitable for precise measurements, mapping, and overlay with other geospatial data.

Orthorectification is not a standalone process; it relies on additional geospatial data to model and correct the image geometry accurately. The two primary components required are:

Digital Elevation Model (DEM): a raster representation of the Earth's surface, where each pixel contains a value representing elevation (height) at that specific location (Yoon, 2008). DEMs are essential for understanding how the topography of the terrain affects the image geometry and for compensating for elevation-related distortions. There are two main types of DEMs:

- Digital Terrain Model (DTM): represents the bare-earth surface, excluding any features such as buildings, vegetation, or other man-made or natural objects. It is used when the focus is on the true underlying ground elevation and is particularly important for applications like hydrological modeling, landform analysis, and contour generation (Lê et al., 2022).
- Digital Surface Model (DSM): includes all surface features, both natural and artificial, such as trees, buildings, and infrastructure. DSMs are used when the height of objects

⁴ <https://github.com/strath-ai/satellite-cloud-removal-dip>

on the surface is relevant, for example, in urban planning, visibility analysis, or 3D modeling of cityscapes (Karatsiolis et al., 2022).

Both DTM and DSM are often derived from remote sensing data using techniques such as LiDAR, stereo photogrammetry, or radar interferometry.

Figure 21 Different Digital Elevation Models: DTM and DSM.⁵

Pixel-to-Terrain Mapping Information: to perform orthorectification, it is also necessary to establish a mathematical relationship between image pixels (in the 2D image coordinate system) and their corresponding locations on the Earth's surface (in geographic or projected coordinates). This mapping can be achieved using one or both of the following methods:

- Rational Polynomial Coefficients (RPCs): RPCs are a widely used method to model the relationship between image space and ground space (Gao et al., 2021). They provide a set of coefficients that approximate the transformation from ground coordinates (latitude, longitude, elevation) to image coordinates (row, column) using rational polynomial equations. This model offers a compact, sensor-independent representation of image geometry and is commonly provided as metadata with many high-resolution satellite products. RPCs are particularly useful when the exact physical sensor model is not available.
- Ground Control Points (GCPs): GCPs are specific, well-identified locations on the Earth's surface with known geographic coordinates (Zhong et al., 2016). These points are typically derived from GPS surveys or high-accuracy maps and are visually identifiable in the satellite or aerial image. By aligning these known locations with their corresponding image pixels, the orthorectification process can precisely anchor the image to real-world positions. GCPs improve the overall geometric accuracy of the orthorectified image and are especially useful when the metadata or RPCs are inaccurate or absent.

While GCPs can enhance orthorectification quality, their collection requires fieldwork or access to high-precision geospatial data, which may not always be available. In many practical

⁵ https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Digital-Elevation-Model-22_fig5_346397975

workflows, GCPs are used to refine or validate the results of an initial orthorectification based on RPCs.

Figure 22 Geometric distortion due to off-nadir satellite viewing angle.⁶

From a software implementation perspective, tools like GDAL (Geospatial Data Abstraction Library) offer practical solutions for performing orthorectification. Using the 'gdalwarp' command, for example, one can input a satellite image along with its corresponding RPC file and a DEM to generate an orthorectified output. The command handles the transformation of each pixel based on the RPCs and terrain data, outputting a georeferenced image that is corrected for geometric distortion. Before executing this, it's often necessary to reproject the DEM to match the coordinate reference system of the satellite image, ensuring accurate alignment during the processing of elevation changes, ensuring that features appearing on slopes or ridges are properly repositioned in the final output.

The quality of the final orthorectified image is influenced by several factors. The spatial resolution and vertical accuracy of the DEM play a major role, as coarse or outdated elevation data can lead to misplaced features, especially in mountainous or uneven terrain. Likewise, the accuracy of GCPs determines the extent to which localized geometric errors can be corrected. When carefully implemented, however, the orthorectification process results in imagery that is spatially accurate and consistent, making it suitable for applications such as land use monitoring, infrastructure planning, and temporal change analysis.

It is worth noting that many satellite imagery providers offer pre-orthorectified products, which are often processed using proprietary physical sensor models and high-resolution global DEMs, which can provide a level of precision difficult to replicate in open workflows. Nevertheless, the ability to perform custom orthorectification remains essential when working with raw data, in areas lacking vendor support, or when higher control over the correction parameters is required.

⁶ <https://www.intermap.com/blog/orthorectification-in-a-nutshell>

Figure 23. Application of a Digital Elevation Model to raw imagery for orthorectification.⁷

5.2.2 Specific needs

For the purposes of this project, not all datasets require orthorectification. In some cases, the imagery is already delivered in an orthorectified format, while in others, the geometric distortions introduced by terrain variation or Earth curvature are negligible due to the nature of the data acquisition. As such, no further orthorectification is needed for the following data sources:

- Sentinel-2: both Level-1C (Top-of-Atmosphere reflectance) and Level-2A (Bottom-of-Atmosphere reflectance) Sentinel-2 products are distributed in an orthorectified format. These products are processed using the ESA’s geometric correction pipeline, which includes the application of precise orbital parameters, sensor modelling, and a global DEM to correct terrain-induced distortions. As a result, no RPC metadata is included or required for further geometric correction.
- EnMAP: EnMAP data is pre-processed using a Geometric Correction Processor, which applies orthorectification as part of the standard workflow. This includes image resampling and correction through either automatically extracted Ground Control Points (GCPs) or predefined sensor models. The resulting products are spatially accurate and aligned to geographic coordinate systems, eliminating the need for additional orthorectification steps.
- Airborne data: aerial imagery collected via aircraft occurs at relatively low altitudes, where the effects of terrain-induced distortions and Earth curvature are minimal, especially over small to medium-sized regions. Due to this limited geometric deviation, such data can be considered spatially accurate without requiring orthorectification, especially when flight paths are well-controlled and modern sensors with GPS/IMU integration are used.

⁷ <https://www.intermap.com/blog/orthorectification-in-a-nutshell>

Given this context, the only dataset within the scope of this project that will require explicit orthorectification is PRISMA, which unlike other dataset, is not delivered in an orthorectified format by default.

5.2.3 Orbview

An orthorectification model inspired by the Orbview model approach has been implemented. This model is designed to correct geometric distortions in satellite imagery, ensuring that the resulting images accurately represent the Earth's surface.

Github - <https://github.com/mpfaffenberger/orthorectification> (MIT license)

5.2.4 Architecture

The Orbview model utilizes Rational Polynomial Coefficients (RPCs) to correct geometric distortions in satellite imagery. This process ensures that each image pixel is accurately mapped to a corresponding location on the Earth's surface, accounting for variations caused by terrain relief, satellite viewing geometry, and sensor orientation.

At its core, the model utilizes a compact representation of the complex relationship between image space and geographic coordinates. Rather than relying on a full physical sensor model, which can be prohibitively complex and sensor-specific, RPCs provide an empirical approximation in the form of ratios between polynomial expressions. This makes them highly portable and widely supported across image providers and processing software.

Figure 24 Geometric misalignment between camera and world coordinates.⁸

The orthorectification pipeline begins by extracting RPCs embedded within the satellite imagery metadata. These coefficients establish a mathematical mapping from ground coordinates (latitude, longitude, and elevation) to image pixel positions. Elevation data is then sourced from a Digital Elevation Model (DEM), which is aligned spatially to the image footprint. The use of a DEM allows the model to correct parallax effects introduced by terrain

⁸ <https://edgybees.com/rpc-rational-polynomial-camera-model-the-nitty-gritty/>

elevation differences, an essential step for high-accuracy applications like topographic mapping or urban planning.

Next, using the bounding coordinates of the target area, a new georeferenced grid is constructed. For each pixel in this output grid, the system computes the geographic coordinates and retrieves the corresponding elevation value from the DEM. These three-dimensional ground points are then projected back into the original image space using the inverse RPC model to interpolate the correct radiometric value. This process, effectively reversing the imaging geometry, yields an orthoimage in which all ground features appear in their true map positions, as if viewed from directly overhead.

5.2.5 Inputs needed

To generate an orthorectified image using the Orbview approach, several essential data inputs are required to correct terrain-induced distortions and align the imagery with real-world geographic coordinates. These inputs form the basis for precise georeferencing and elevation correction within the orthorectification pipeline:

- Raw Image: this is the original, uncorrected satellite image that still contains geometric distortions caused by terrain relief, sensor angle, and Earth's curvature. These distortions result in spatial inaccuracies, particularly in areas with significant elevation changes.
- Digital Elevation Model: the implementation uses the sardem library (<https://github.com/scottstanie/sardem>) to automatically generate DEMs, providing sufficient terrain resolution and offering accurate elevation details that will significantly enhance the geometric precision of the orthorectified outputs.
- Boundary Vector: A shapefile containing polygonal boundary data is used to define the geographic extent of the image or the area of interest (AOI). This ensures that the orthorectification process is spatially constrained and aligned with the known footprint of the image. The coordinates within the shapefile assist in anchoring the imagery to real-world map geometry.
- RPCs: these will be provided as part of the image metadata, specifically from PRISMA satellite products.

Together, these inputs allow the Orbview orthorectification workflow to produce geometrically corrected, map-aligned satellite images that can be reliably integrated with other geospatial datasets. With the incorporation of flight-derived DTM/DSM data, a significant increase in spatial accuracy and consistency across multi-source imagery used in the project is expected as the system evolves.

5.2.6 Use example

Due to the current unavailability of PRISMA satellite imagery, an example was conducted using the default data provided by the Orbview model:

Figure 25 Raw image (left) and orthorectified image (right) corrected using the Orbview sensor model.

Although the two images may appear similar at first glance, the image on the right is the orthorectified version, as can be observed in the altered shapes and positions of terrain features (most notably, the hills near the top and bottom edges of the scene). These changes reflect the correction of geometric distortions caused by terrain relief and off-nadir viewing angles in the original image. As a result, the orthorectified image presents a more accurate, map-like representation of the Earth's surface, with features appearing in their true geographic positions.

6. Pilots testing

This section presents the results of remote sensing analyses carried out over each pilot site, based on imagery from three different sources: Sentinel-2, PRISMA, and airborne data. Each data source has been processed using distinct TL2 methods implemented into the ARD framework to extract relevant information. The subsections below describe the approaches applied and the outcomes obtained for each data source. Please note that orthorectification models only apply to PRISMA data, since Sentinel-2 and airborne data are already orthorectified.

6.1 Canteras

6.1.1 Sentinel-2

For Sentinel-2 imagery, as TL2 algorithm, cloud masking was applied. Orthorectification was not necessary, as the Sentinel-2 images used are already orthorectified at the time of acquisition.

In the cloud masking stage, the primary objective was to eliminate the influence of clouds in the optical imagery to ensure the integrity of the data used for analysis. This was achieved using the SRC-DIP model, which effectively filtered out cloud-contaminated pixels. When applying SRC-DIP to Cantera's data, several adjustments are necessary. Both the codebase and the data inputs must be adapted to accommodate differences in image format, mask generation, and specific characteristics of the datasets to ensure optimal performance and accurate

The following example demonstrates the application of the SCR-DIP model on a Sentinel-2 Level-2A satellite image of the Canteras mine in Granada. Since the model operates on fixed-size inputs, both the cloud-affected image (raw) and the reference image (ground truth) were resized to 256×256 pixels prior to processing:

Figure 26 Sentinel-2 images of the Canteras mines, showing a cloud-covered scene (raw image) and a cloud-free ground truth acquired at different times.

The cloud and shadow masks are derived from the Scene Classification Layer (SCL) of the Sentinel-2 TL2A product (Sanchez et al., 2024). These masks define which areas of the image are obstructed and need reconstruction. The relevant SCL classes used to create binary masks are:

- Class 3: cloud shadows, areas shaded on the ground by clouds blocking sunlight.
- Class 7: low-probability clouds, pixels that might be clouds, but the algorithm is not very confident.
- Class 8: medium-probability clouds, pixels likely to be clouds, with moderate confidence.
- Class 9: high-probability clouds, pixels very likely to be clouds, with high confidence.

Figure 27 Scene Classification Layer classes 3, 7, 8 and 9, respectively.

Figure 28 Whole merged cloud and shadow mask.

Once these inputs are prepared, the SCR-DIP model performs its internal learning-based inpainting process. The output is a corrected satellite image in which cloud-covered and shadowed regions have been filled in using information from the cloud-free regions of the raw image and the structural cues from the ground truth image. The result is a visually coherent and usable image, free of atmospheric obstructions and suitable for downstream analysis.

Figure 29 Raw image (top-left), ground truth reference (top-right), cloud and shadow mask (bottom-left), and SCR-DIP reconstruction (bottom-right).

6.1.2 EnMAP

At this stage of the project, EnMAP imagery has not yet been incorporated into the analysis. The use of EnMAP data is scheduled for future phases.

6.1.3 PRISMA

At this stage of the project, PRISMA imagery has not yet been incorporated into the analysis. The use of PRISMA data is scheduled for future phases.

6.1.4 Airborne

At this stage of the project, Airborne imagery has not yet been incorporated into the analysis. The use of Airborne data is scheduled for future phases.

6.2 Tharsis

6.2.1 Sentinel-2

For Sentinel-2 imagery, as TL2 algorithm, cloud masking was applied. Orthorectification was not necessary, as the Sentinel-2 images used are already orthorectified at the time of acquisition. Experiments were carried out for all of Tharsis, La Zarza and San Telmo mining areas, although these results will be better in the future as the model improves.

For la Zarza mining area, the small image size allowed the model to output a really nice cloud-free image.

Figure 30 Sentinel-2 images of La Zarza mines, showing a cloud-covered scene (16/03/2025) and a cloud-free ground truth (14/02/2025).

Figure 31 Raw image (top-left), ground truth reference (top-right), cloud and shadow mask (bottom-left), and SCR-DIP reconstruction (bottom-right).

For the San Telmo mining area, the procedure was similar, but the final output was not so high-quality as the latter, probably due to the high presence of clouds in the raw image.

Figure 32 Sentinel-2 images of San Telmo mines, showing a cloud-covered scene (03/04/2024) and a cloud-free ground truth (15/04/2024).

Figure 33 Raw image (top-left), ground truth reference (top-right), cloud and shadow mask (bottom-left), and SCR-DIP reconstruction (bottom-right).

For the Tharsis main mining area, the higher size of the region, and the fact that bigger images tend to be darker, the model did not perform well, but this will be looked into and improved in the future.

Figure 34 Sentinel-2 images of Tharsis mines, showing a cloud-covered scene (28/01/2025) and a cloud-free ground truth (30/01/2025).

Figure 35 Raw image (top-left), ground truth reference (top-right), cloud and shadow mask (bottom-left), and SCR-DIP reconstruction (bottom-right).

6.2.2 EnMAP

At this stage of the project, EnMAP imagery has not yet been incorporated into the analysis. The use of EnMAP data is scheduled for future phases.

6.2.3 PRISMA

At this stage of the project, PRISMA imagery has not yet been incorporated into the analysis. The use of PRISMA data is scheduled for future phases.

6.2.4 Airborne

At this stage of the project, airborne imagery for Tharsis has not yet been incorporated into the analysis and will be included in future versions of the deliverable.

6.3 Terna Mag

6.3.1 Sentinel-2

For Sentinel-2 imagery, as TL2 algorithm, cloud masking was applied. Orthorectification was not necessary, as the Sentinel-2 images used are already orthorectified at the time of acquisition. Experiments were carried out for one of Terna Mag's mining areas, although these results will be better in the future as the model improves.

The bigger size of Terna Mag regions usually cause the images to be darker when clouds are present in the image, making a high-quality prediction hard for the model to generate.

Figure 36 Sentinel-2 images of Terna Mag mining area, showing a cloud-covered scene (06/04/2025) and a cloud-free ground truth (10/03/2025).

Figure 37 Raw image (top-left), ground truth reference (top-right), cloud and shadow mask (bottom-left), and SCR-DIP reconstruction (bottom-right).

It is worth noting that when certain Terna Mag data is fed into the model, artifacts occasionally appear on the input images, manifesting as scattered blue and red patches. These artifacts may impact the final output and will be investigated further in future work.

6.3.2 EnMAP

At this stage of the project, EnMAP imagery has not yet been incorporated into the analysis. The use of EnMAP data is scheduled for future phases.

6.3.3 PRISMA

At this stage of the project, PRISMA imagery has not yet been incorporated into the analysis. The use of PRISMA data is scheduled for future phases.

7. TERRAVISION's ARD Framework vs other approaches

The TERRAVISION framework for processing Analysis Ready Data (ARD) introduces significant novelties through the intrinsic integration of semantic enrichment techniques and Artificial Intelligence (AI) inference mechanisms across the data lifecycle, in support of mining site monitoring tasks (deformations of overlay terrain, slope stability, raw materials spectral analysis, stockpile volume surveying, ambient air quality, ...), and with a particular emphasis on data integration in Earth Observation (EO), plane observation and sensor. This methodology represents a notable advancement when compared to the current state-of-the-art in ARD generation.

From a technical standpoint, the central innovation is found within its four-layer architecture (TL1 to TL4). While raw data ingestion and normalization are handled by TL1, and the preprocessing to generate radiometric and geometric harmonisation (including algorithms such as cloud masking inspired by SCR-DIP and orthorectification) is the focus of TL2, it is in TL3 and TL4 that the system fundamentally moves beyond traditional ARD concepts. Advanced AI models are applied in TL3, the Feature Analysis & Inference Layer, to extract semantic information from the Layer 2 harmonised datasets. Alpha algorithms, including object detection utilizing models like Detrex and GroundedSAM2, and change detection with architectures such as MineNetCD, are detailed. Importantly, these not only identify patterns but also interpret image content, leading to the generation of semantic metadata and structured knowledge concerning, for instance, the presence and location of specific features in mining sites or their temporal evolution. Consequently, the ARD approach to “readiness for analysis (in relation to a defined user task)” is ensured to be not merely radiometrically and geometrically corrected data, but data enriched with a meaningful semantic layer tailored to support the Mining sites monitoring tasks. The Fusion Layer, TL4, further deepens this semantic exploitation and AI application. It is tasked with the intelligent collation, fusion, and advanced post-processing of outputs from preceding layers. A key novelty highlighted here is its capacity for generating semantically rich narratives and facilitating Visual Question Answering (VQA) systems, exemplified by a custom LLaVA model fine-tuned for interpreting satellite imagery and responding to queries in natural language. This capability allows for the transformation of complex geospatial data and AI inferences into actionable, human-understandable insights.

A comparison with the state-of-the-art (SOTA) reveals distinct advancements. Current SOTA in ARD, as seen in initiatives like USGS Landsat Collections, Copernicus Sentinel L2A products, and CEOS ARD specifications, is primarily concerned with ensuring data are radiometrically and geometrically consistent, devoid of significant atmospheric and sensor-induced artifacts, and prepared for direct scientific analysis or as input to subsequent, often separate, AI/ML workflows. Such ARD products, crucial for interoperability and time-series analysis, generally culminate at what TERRAVISION defines as TL2 outputs.

TERRAVISION is differentiated by several key aspects. A deep semantic integration within the ARD generation process itself is achieved; while SOTA ARD is considered "AI-ready,"

TERRAVISION aims to produce ARD that is already "AI-derived and semantically-rich." The semantic understanding (TL3) and intelligent interpretation (TL4) are not treated as post-processing steps to be performed by the end-user on standard ARD, but are integral parts of the TERRAVISION framework's output, with the framework itself orchestrating the generation of these semantic layers. Furthermore, the framework moves beyond mere preprocessing to interpretation. Traditional ARD pipelines correct data; TERRAVISION utilizes these corrected data (ARD from TL2) as a foundation for immediate, embedded AI-driven interpretation. The inclusion of specific AI models for object detection and change detection within TL3, and sophisticated VQA and narrative generation using fine-tuned Large Language and Vision Models in TL4, directly within the ARD processing chain, is a significant step forward, contrasting with SOTA where users often apply their own separate AI toolchains to ARD.

Actionable, interpretable outputs are also established as core products. While SOTA ARD delivers corrected imagery and basic metadata, TERRAVISION's TL4 is designed to deliver human-understandable narratives and answers to visual questions directly derived from the imagery and AI analysis, thus moving beyond data provision to insight generation within the same unified framework. This level of integrated semantic output is not standard in ARD production. Architectural support for evolving AI is another distinction; the modular, JSON-driven, and extensible architecture is explicitly designed to facilitate the continuous integration and experimentation with new semantic techniques and AI models, offering greater flexibility than many existing ARD production systems in directly incorporating rapidly evolving AI capabilities. Finally, a holistic workflow is provided for domain-specific applications such as mining. The entire pipeline, from diverse data ingestion to intelligent output, is tailored for the mining lifecycle. While SOTA ARD can be utilized in mining applications, TERRAVISION provides an end-to-end, semantically-aware framework specifically designed and optimized for this domain.

In essence, the incentive for using semantic and AI techniques within the ARD process, as proposed by TERRAVISION, is rooted in the transformation of EO data from mere corrected pixels into contextualized, interpretable information. This allows for deeper analyses, predictive monitoring, and more robust and efficient decision-support systems, which are particularly crucial for the complex demands of the mining lifecycle. The approach adopted by TERRAVISION signifies a shift from a primarily data-centric ARD to a more knowledge-centric ARD paradigm, where intelligence is directly embedded into the data products.

8. Code published in GitHub

The Ard-Terravision project’s complete source code is publicly accessible under the ITA-TECNOLOGIA organization on GitHub at <https://github.com/ITA-TECNOLOGIA/Ard-Terravision>. The project is released under the MIT License, with the full license text included in the LICENSE file at the root of the repository.

At the top level, the repository is organized into clearly named directories and configuration files that reflect its layered pipeline architecture. There is a `.vscode/` folder for editor settings, a `figures/` directory for visual assets, `pipelines/` containing example JSON configurations, and a `src/` directory housing the core processing modules for layers L1 through L4. The root also includes environment and helper files—`.env`, `.gitignore`, and `.gitmodules`—alongside the critical `README.md` and `LICENSE` files, ensuring that both development practices and licensing requirements are immediately visible. The file tree of the repo can be shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 38 Repository file tree showing `.vscode/`, `figures/`, `pipelines/`, `src/`, and root files, published in GitHub.

The `README.md` provides a comprehensive table of contents, guiding readers through sections on Architecture Overview, Description, Installation, Usage, Testing, Pipeline Configuration (L1–L4), extending the pipeline with custom algorithms, Data Sources, Roadmap, Authors & Acknowledgments, License, and Project Status. Its introductory paragraph succinctly explains that Ard-Terravision “contains scripts, utilities, and a modular pipeline to produce Analysis Ready Data from satellite and airborne imagery,” highlighting the streamlined flow from raw inputs to geospatially enriched outputs. A screenshot of the `README` file can be observed in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 39 Screenshot of README landing page with header, and license badge.

In the Architecture Overview section, a flow diagram graphically depicts the four-layer pipeline: L1 for data ingestion, L2 for preprocessing and corrections (e.g., atmospheric correction, orthorectification), L3 for feature extraction and AI-driven inference, and L4 for collating outputs into final deliverables. Figure 40 clarifies how raw Sentinel-2 and airborne imagery progress through successive transformations.

Figure 40 Pipeline architecture diagram showing L1 → L4 workflow.

The Installation section walks users through setting up a Python environment (e.g., `conda create -n terravision_ard python=3.10`), configuring GPU usage via a `.env` file, installing core dependencies (`pip install python-dotenv, PyTorch with CUDA 12.6`, and `pip install -r`

src/main/requirements.txt), and obtaining pretrained model checkpoints for modules like Grounded-SAM-2. Including a snippet of these commands—cloning the repo, activating the environment, and installing dependencies—will help readers follow along easily. This can be observed in Figure 41.

Installation

- 1. Create a Python environment (recommended conda):**

```
conda create -n terravision_ard python=3.10
conda activate terravision_ard
```
- 2. Create a .env file at the project root with your desired device setting:**

```
DEVICE=cuda:1
```

The pipeline will load this environment variable (using `python-dotenv`) to configure GPU usage for all algorithms.
- 3. Install dependencies:**

```
pip install python-dotenv
```
- 4. Install PyTorch (with CUDA 12.6 support):**

Since the environment has been tested on `salas.ita.es` with `CUDA 12.6`:

```
pip3 install torch torchvision torchaudio --index-url https://download.pytorch.org/whl/cu126
```
- 5. Install the core dependencies:**

```
pip install -r src/main/requirements.txt
```
- 6. Install Grounded-SAM-2 and dependencies:**

```
pip install -e src/main/python/L3/ObjectDetection/Grounded-SAM-2
pip install src/main/python/L3/ObjectDetection/Grounded-SAM-2[demo]
pip install --no-build-isolation -e src/main/python/L3/ObjectDetection/Grounded-SAM-2/grounding_dir
```
- 7. Download and move pretrained checkpoints:**

```
bash src/main/python/L3/ObjectDetection/Grounded-SAM-2/checkpoints/download_ckpts.sh
mv sam2.1_hiera_*.pt checkpoints/
```

Figure 41 Installation command snippet from README.

Under Usage, the primary entry point is invoked with:

```
python src/main/python/main.py --config pipelines/satellite_example.json
```

which loads environment variables and executes the configured pipeline. The subsequent Testing section prescribes running unit tests via:

```
python -m unittest discover -v -s src/test/python
```

Pipeline Configuration is handled entirely through JSON files, each describing keys l1_input, l2_algorithms, l3_algorithms, and l4_algorithm with corresponding type and params. A JSON example can be observed in Figure 42.


```

1 {
2   "l1_input": {
3     "type": "satellite",
4     "params": {
5       "satellite_path": "/data/ssd/projects/terravision/terravision_satellite_32x32_CenterAI_AOI_2004-03-14_2005-03-14_batch_with_clouds.nc"
6     }
7   },
8   "l2_algorithms": [
9     {
10      "type": "AtmosphericCorrection",
11      "params": {
12        "line_indices": [1],
13        "band_names": ["B02", "B03", "B04"]
14      }
15    },
16    {
17      "type": "CloudMasking",
18      "params": {
19        "line_indices": [17],
20        "top_band_names": ["B04", "B03", "B02"]
21      }
22    },
23    {
24      "type": "PanSharpening",
25      "params": {
26        "line_indices": [1],
27        "band_names": ["B02", "B03", "B04"]
28      }
29    }
30  ],
31   "l4_algorithm": {

```

Figure 42 Example JSON configuration snippet from satellite example.

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```

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19 Copyright (c) 2024 ITA-TECNOLOGIA
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Figure 43 Screenshot of the MIT License published in the GitHub repository.

9. Towards the ARD FRAMEWORK version 2

The TERRAVISION ARD framework version 1, detailed within this deliverable, has achieved a significant developmental stage, marked by the successful implementation and initial testing of its fundamental architectural components alongside alpha-versions of pivotal algorithms across the four distinct TERRAVISION Layers (TL1-TL4). The JSON-driven configuration system, coupled with a flexible plugin architecture facilitated by a class registry, is now operational. Furthermore, the foundational L1 data ingestion modules, designed to handle inputs from sources like Sentinel and Airborne platforms, are functioning effectively, establishing a solid and reliable platform primed for subsequent development and enhancement. Algorithms addressing critical pre-processing tasks within TL2, specifically Cloud Masking and Orthorectification, have been developed. Similarly, initial AI-driven analytical capabilities have been integrated into TL3, with Object Detection and Change Detection algorithms demonstrating promising outcomes on preliminary pilot datasets. These early successes serve to validate the core design choices and underscore the inherent potential of the framework. The L4 fusion layer, notably featuring its LLaVACustom implementation, effectively showcases the framework's capacity for advanced semantic interpretation and the generation of meaningful narratives from processed data.

Currently, the layered architecture (TL1-TL4) stands implemented and stable, with established data flow mechanisms between layers, all orchestrated by the flexible JSON configuration that allows for dynamic pipeline definition. Core abstractions and interfaces, crucial for modularity and future expansion, are defined and largely adhered to across the system. The L1 data ingestion modules for primary Earth Observation data sources pertinent to the pilot project needs are fully functional, capably reading, normalizing, and preparing data for the subsequent TL2 pre-processing stage. Within TL2, the alpha versions of Cloud Masking and Orthorectification algorithms are integrated. While they demonstrate functionality, these algorithms necessitate further refinement, comprehensive validation across the full spectrum of pilot sites and diverse data types, and targeted performance optimization. In addition, Cloud Masking supports use cases in T9.1 (exploration), T9.4 (material mapping), and T9.5 (hazard prediction), where reliable atmospheric filtering is essential for downstream analytics. The integration of mature Atmospheric Correction and Pan-Sharpening modules remains a key activity for this layer, for second version of this deliverable. Moving to TL3, the alpha versions of Object Detection and Change Detection algorithms are operational. Initial tests conducted on pilot data indicate their applicability to mining scenarios, but extensive tuning, rigorous training on larger and more diverse datasets specific to TERRAVISION use cases, and thorough performance benchmarking are essential next steps. The integration of other planned TL3 algorithms, such as LULC Classification and Semantic Segmentation tailored for mining environments, is an ongoing process. The TL4 output and semantic fusion layer, particularly through the LLaVACustom module, has demonstrated significant potential for semantic output. Further dedicated work is required to refine prompting strategies, enhance the model's domain-specific knowledge relevant to the mining sector, and effectively integrate outputs from multiple TL3 algorithms into cohesive, comprehensive reports or interactive visualizations. The project's codebase is actively managed on GitHub, with initial CI/CD pipelines potentially in place to support basic testing and code quality linting.

Established practices for dependency management via requirements.txt and environment configuration using .env files are also in effect. Initial phases of pilot testing have commenced, involving data from the Canteras, Tharsis, and Terna Mag sites for select algorithms, yielding valuable early feedback crucial for algorithm refinement.

To propel the ARD framework from its current advanced v1 stage to its final, fully realized version 2, a series of focused next steps are planned. Firstly, a paramount activity will be the iterative refinement and comprehensive validation of all algorithms within TL2, TL3, and TL4. This involves continuously improving existing alpha-version algorithms based on detailed feedback from ongoing pilot testing and rigorous internal evaluations, specifically addressing identified limitations, enhancing accuracy, and bolstering robustness across varied geographical areas and sensor types. Rigorous validation of all algorithms will be conducted using verified ground truth data sourced from the pilot sites, establishing clear Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for each algorithm and benchmarking performance against these metrics. The development and seamless integration of any remaining algorithms outlined in the project's work plan, such as more sophisticated atmospheric correction techniques or LULC classifiers specifically designed for complex mining landscapes, will be prioritized. For the AI-based algorithms in TL3 and TL4, there will be an expansion of training datasets, incorporating more diverse and representative samples from all TERRAVISION pilot sites, alongside extensive hyperparameter tuning and meticulous fine-tuning of pre-trained models like LLaVA to optimize their performance within mining-specific contexts. Crucially, a significant component of future work involves the full integration and operationalization of the in-situ sensor data pipeline. This encompasses the development and deployment of robust TL1 modules specifically designed to ingest, validate, and process data streams originating from the various sensors once their installation across pilot sites is complete. The subsequent processing of this numerical sensor data, and its fusion with Earth Observation data within the TL3 and TL4 layers, will be a key focus to unlock synergistic analytical capabilities and provide a more holistic understanding of mining operations and their environmental context. In particular, the generation and analysis of Temporal Series data is central to T9.5 (hazard prediction), enabling dynamic monitoring and trend detection over time. This will require careful design of data formats, communication protocols, and analytical modules capable of handling heterogeneous time-series data alongside geospatial imagery.

Secondly, significant effort will be dedicated to enhancing the overall robustness and usability of the framework. This includes improving error handling mechanisms across all layers and augmenting logging capabilities to ensure better traceability and facilitate more efficient debugging. The entire pipeline will be profiled to identify and address performance bottlenecks, with computationally intensive modules, particularly in TL2 and TL3, being optimized for speed and resource efficiency through techniques like parallelization or the adoption of more efficient libraries. Technical documentation for developers, encompassing API specifications and detailed algorithm descriptions, will be expanded and refined, concurrently with the development of user guides tailored for service providers who will ultimately consume the ARD and TL4 outputs. The Streamlit interface, or alternative visualization tools, will undergo further development to improve demonstration capabilities, debugging workflows, and user interaction with the pipeline's intermediate and final products. Furthermore, the framework's extensibility will be actively leveraged through the

introduction of new modules and functionalities in TL2, TL3, and TL4. These additions will be driven directly by the evolving requirements and specific needs identified by the service providers and end-users within the TERRAVISION consortium, ensuring the final platform is precisely tailored to deliver maximum value and address real-world operational challenges in the mining sector.

Thirdly, full-scale pilot testing will be systematically rolled out, involving the deployment of the evolving framework across all three designated pilot sites—Canteras, Tharsis, and Terna Mag—to process a wider and more challenging range of data scenarios, including the newly integrated sensor data streams. A structured and continuous feedback loop will be established with service provider partners to gather critical input on ARD quality, algorithm performance, the utility of fused sensor-EO data products, and the overall usability and practicality of the framework. This feedback will be actively incorporated into ongoing development cycles, ensuring that the final framework precisely meets the practical and operational needs of its end-users. Furthermore, any specific requirements for deploying or interfacing the framework, or its constituent parts, with OpenEO platforms will be addressed, ensuring API compatibility and efficient execution within such distributed environments.

Finally, considerations for scalability and deployment readiness will be vital. The framework's ability to handle significantly larger data volumes and increased processing demands, especially with the inclusion of continuous sensor data, will be thoroughly assessed and enhanced as needed. Preparations for potential deployment in operational environments will include exploring aspects such as containerization using technologies like Docker, orchestration via platforms such as Kubernetes, and seamless integration with robust data storage solutions. By systematically addressing these multifaceted next steps, the TERRAVISION framework will successfully transition to a mature, robust, and thoroughly validated final version.

10. Conclusion

This deliverable has meticulously presented the comprehensive design, detailed implementation, and current developmental status of the ARD framework. The fundamental objective underpinning this framework is the consistent generation of high-quality Analysis Ready Data and the derivation of actionable, insightful information, all geared towards supporting and significantly enhancing the entire mining life cycle of critical raw materials. Through its modular four-layer architecture, designated as TL1 through TL4, the framework systematically processes a diverse range of Earth Observation data. This journey transforms raw inputs through meticulous ingestion and pre-processing stages, progressing to advanced AI-driven analysis and culminating in sophisticated semantic interpretation.

The development efforts undertaken thus far have successfully established a robust, flexible, and highly capable platform. Key achievements to date prominently include the operationalization of a clearly defined layered architecture, characterized by well-delineated interfaces and distinct layer responsibilities. This architecture is effectively managed by a JSON-driven configuration system, a design choice that inherently promotes adaptability to diverse use cases and ensures the reproducibility of results. Foundational data ingestion modules within TL1 have been implemented and are fully capable of handling the key satellite and airborne data sources identified as relevant to the project's objectives. Furthermore, the development and initial validation of alpha-version algorithms for critical ARD generation steps within TL2, such as Cloud Masking and Orthorectification, have been successfully completed, alongside similar progress for advanced information extraction algorithms in TL3, including Object Detection and Change Detection, that has been presented in deliverable D7.5. A compelling demonstration of semantic fusion and narrative generation capabilities within TL4, notably through the LLaVACustom module, effectively highlights the framework's advanced potential to translate complex, voluminous data into human-understandable and actionable insights. The project has also consistently adopted sound software engineering practices, including rigorous version control, systematic dependency management, and the establishment of initial testing procedures, all of which lay a strong foundation for a system that is both maintainable and readily extensible in the future.

The initial results derived from applying these alpha-version algorithms to real-world data from the designated TERRAVISION pilot sites—Canteras, Tharsis, and Terna Mag—are decidedly promising. These outcomes serve to validate the core conceptual underpinnings of the framework and affirm its substantial potential to effectively address the unique and often complex challenges inherent in the mining sector. The systematic and layered approach adopted ensures that raw observations are consistently transformed into harmonized, high-quality datasets. These datasets can then be exploited efficiently and confidently by consortium partners and, eventually, by external users, thereby maximizing their analytical value.

Looking forward, the trajectory towards achieving the final, fully operational version of the TERRAVISION framework involves a dedicated phase of continued refinement of all existing algorithms, the seamless integration of additional planned functionalities, and rigorous, comprehensive validation across the full spectrum of pilot scenarios. Performance

optimization will also remain a key focus to ensure operational efficiency. The active and continuous feedback loop established with service provider partners will be absolutely crucial in shaping a final tool that is not only technologically advanced and innovative but also demonstrably practical and impactful for the mining industry and its stakeholders.

11. Bibliography

- Boccardo, P., Borgogno Mondino, E. C., FABIO GIULIO TONOLO, & Lingua, A. (2004). *Orthorectification of high resolution satellite images*. <https://iris.unito.it/handle/2318/103885>
- Czerkawski, M., Upadhyay, P., Davison, C., Werkmeister, A., Cardona, J., Atkinson, R., Michie, C., Andonovic, I., Macdonald, M., & Tachtatzis, C. (2022). Deep Internal Learning for inpainting of Cloud-Affected Regions in Satellite Imagery. *Remote Sensing*, 14(6), 1342. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14061342>
- Gao, J., Liu, J., & Ji, S. (2021). *Rational Polynomial Camera Model Warping for Deep Learning Based Satellite Multi-View Stereo Matching* (No. arXiv:2109.11121). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2109.11121>
- Karatsiolis, S., Padubidri, C., & Kamilaris, A. (2022). Exploiting Digital Surface Models for Inferring Super-Resolution for Remotely Sensed Images. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 60, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2022.3209340>
- Laszewski, G. von, & Gu, R. (2023). *An Overview of MLCommons Cloud Mask Benchmark: Related Research and Data* (No. arXiv:2312.04799). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2312.04799>
- Lê, H.-Â., Guiotte, F., Pham, M.-T., Lefèvre, S., & Corpetti, T. (2022). *Learning Digital Terrain Models from Point Clouds: ALS2DTM Dataset and Rasterization-based GAN* (No. arXiv:2206.03778). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2206.03778>
- O'Shea, K., & Nash, R. (2015). *An Introduction to Convolutional Neural Networks* (No. arXiv:1511.08458). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1511.08458>
- Sanchez, C., Mena, F., Charfuelan, M., Nuske, M., & Dengel, A. (2024). Assessment of Sentinel-2 spatial and temporal coverage based on the scene classification layer. *IGARSS 2024 - 2024 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, 4099-4103. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS53475.2024.10642213>
- Ulyanov, D., Vedaldi, A., & Lempitsky, V. (2020). Deep Image Prior. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 128(7), 1867-1888. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11263-020-01303-4>
- Wright, N., Duncan, J. M. A., Callow, J. N., Thompson, S. E., & George, R. J. (2024). CloudS2Mask: A novel deep learning approach for improved cloud and cloud shadow masking in Sentinel-2 imagery. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 306, 114122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2024.114122>
- Yoon, J.-S. (2008). Ortho-rectification of a Digital Aerial Image using LiDAR-derived Elevation Model in Forested Area. *Korean Journal of Remote Sensing*, 24(5), 463-471. <https://doi.org/10.7780/kjrs.2008.24.5.463>

Zhang, Y., Zhao, C., Wu, Y., & Luo, J. (2022). Remote sensing image cloud removal by deep image prior with a multitemporal constraint. *Optics Continuum*, 1(2), 215-226. <https://doi.org/10.1364/OPTCON.439671>

Zhong, Z., Su, S., Cao, D., & Li, S. (2016). *Detecting Ground Control Points via Convolutional Neural Network for Stereo Matching* (No. arXiv:1605.02289). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1605.02289>